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Development of technical recommendations for Nearly Zero Energy Buildings (NZEB) in Ukraine FI05-2022-108/FIN-013-TA

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Summary <p>This report and project address the opportunities for improving energy efficiency, reducing cost and emissions in the building sector by improving energy efficiency, and provides the technical recommendation for nearly zero energy building (NZEB) in Ukraine. Climate change is one of the most significant global challenges that we are facing today. There is a need to dramatically reduce emissions associated with human activities, largely caused by energy production, to mitigate climate change. The first step is to reduce the energy need by improving the energy efficiency of the activities. Another important action is the transition towards renewable energy production. The energy produced on-site in buildings, using building-integrated solar photovoltaic, heat pumps and bioenergy, among others, could form an important share of the energy in an energy ecosystem based on renewables. Consequently, buildings could have a significant role in enabling energy transition and mitigating climate change. In this report two building types are focused on context of Ukraine that are residential apartment building and school building. These are selected as they have significant impact and large share of the building stock in the context of NZEB development. Both the buildings are modelled and simulated on IDA-ICE dynamic simulation software. The buildings are simulated for two climate zones i.e., Kyiv (North) and Odesa (South). This report presents the building layouts and the parameters used in the simulations, as well as the methodology and results of the technical and economical studies. State of the current energy efficiency regulations in Ukraine is also included in the report. Three workshops with the key stakeholders and collaborators and companies were arranged during July 2022 and September 2022 to share information on the on-going project, discuss about the state of the art of the energy regulations and NZEB in Ukraine, as well as collect first hand information on the building design and on the cost. The last workshop was arranged during November 2022, where the main outcomes and findings of the project were disseminated with the local stakeholders.</p> <p>The focus of the study is on the energy efficiency for the buildings. The study was done on reducing the use of heating energy in the buildings. However, this also affected the cooling load and electricity consumption. Between the building types, the main differences affecting the study results were found to be ventilation flow rates, roof area, and different electricity & heat tariffs.</p> <p>The technical assessment showed mostly similar results for both building types, in that the most potential improvement is by considerable margin ventilation heat recovery, and after this window U-value and external wall U-value improvements. For the school building ventilation heat recovery and roof U-value improvements are relatively more potential compared to the apartment building, due to higher ventilation flow rate and roof area, while for the apartment building window U-value improvement was relatively better due to higher glazing to envelope ratio. The economical assessment showed that energy improvements of the apartment building type could only be made profitable with the inclusion of ventilation heat recovery, while for the school building roof U-value upgrade and a moderate window U-value upgrade were also found to be profitable by themselves. However, with the increase in the energy cost, the improvement in the windows, walls, floor, roof, and ventilation heat recovery becomes cost effective solutions for NZEBs. Therefore, to reach NZEB levels it is recommended to move from the state of the are towards improved building envelop and ventilation heat recovery systems for both apartment and school buildings. The policy and building regulations should be made that allows present building sector to make faster transition towards NZEB buildings. Moreover, regulations should make conditions that will reduce the investment cost on energy efficient building components, lower the interest rates, channelize the financial benefits, and provide tax benefits to the construction sector that would construct such buildings in Ukraine.</p> <p>The onsite integration of renewable energy source on the building i.e., photovoltaic (PV) integration showed that the onsite electricity fraction for the apartment building was between 20-25 %, depending on the climatic zone. However, for the school building it varied between 30-47 % depending on the climatic zone. It was found that it was profitability</p>	

to integrate PV for the school building due to its high electricity tariff, generation and consumption matching and larger roof area available. With increase in the energy prices the integration of PV will be beneficial. It is highly recommended to improve energy policy and regulations that will promote PV integration onsite (on buildings) and nearby areas. Regulations should make it easier for the end users to share the excess energy with neighbour, empower the end users by putting them at the centre of the decision making while upgrading the regulations. It is recommended to promote energy storage, energy communities concept and new business models. All this together will support in reducing the energy costs, emissions, energy import and provide energy security and better indoor environment

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1. Introduction and background

1.1 Project background

The last two decades have seen rapid climate change issues with severe droughts, flooding, heat waves and other climate-related crises [1]. According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), the role of human activities in this is evident, and this trend will continue if no efforts are taken to mitigate climate change [2]. The World Economic Forum (2016) puts climate change or the failure to mitigate or adapt to it on top of the risks for the global economy, higher than weapons of mass destruction and water crises. Efforts are taken both on the global and European levels to mitigate the effects of human activities on climate change. The building sector is one of the largest contributors to emissions. To reduce emissions, buildings must be energy efficient and use a significant amount of locally generated renewable energy.

In many districts, cities and regions, buildings are nowadays designed to be nearly zero energy or net zero energy to achieve emission reduction targets and to mitigate climate change [4]. The European Union (EU), through the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) [5] initiated in 2002, adopted in 2006 and updated in 2010 and 2018 and the revised EPBD aims to make all newly-constructed or heavily-renovated buildings adhere to a “nearly zero energy building NZEB” target as of 2021. The policy goal is to decarbonise the whole building stock by 2050. This project is designed to support and provide technical recommendations to Ukraine, which is willing to join the EU, to align and synchronize their national building regulations and framework towards NZEB requirements and definition as stated in the EPBD. This will improve the building efficiency in Ukraine and provide a framework for the local stakeholders to plan and construct buildings according to NZEB requirements.

Moreover, this project will provide a starting point to reconstruct the buildings after the Russian invasion in a better way that can support energy efficiency in the buildings from the beginning. This project will have a big impact in a way that Ukraine can start the reconstruction of the buildings in an energy efficient manner. The best cost optimal NZEB solutions can be taken in use instead of old practice from the beginning. The beneficiary of the project is the Energy Efficiency Directorate in the Ministry of Communities and Territories Development (MCTD) of Ukraine.

1.2 Project objectives

The main objectives of the project are to support the development of technical regulations and requirements for cost-efficient NZEB solutions for new apartment buildings and schools in Ukraine and provide these technical recommendations to the Ministry of Development of Communities and Territories of Ukraine. The development of the proposed project is supporting the first five-year (2020-2025) period of the National Plan. These technical NZEB recommendations will be the further step for the implementation of the NZEB requirements in Ukraine. In Ukraine, there is already a concept for the implementation of state policy in the field of ensuring the energy efficiency of buildings in terms of increasing the number of buildings with close to zero energy consumption [6]. The report will be the basis for the requirements for buildings of NZEB in Ukraine, which have not yet been approved at the legislative level. The resulting NZEB technical recommendations will use the current energy efficiency legislation as a starting point and build up on the current business practice technologies allowing a smooth transition to the cost-efficient NZEB.

1.3 Global perspective to climate change and buildings

The Paris Agreement brings all nations into a common cause to undertake ambitious efforts to combat climate change and adapt to its effects. The goal of the Paris Agreement is to limit global warming to well below 2, preferably to 1.5 °C, compared to pre-industrial levels [7]. According to the initial NDC (Nationally determined contributions) synthesis report, stronger efforts and ambitious action plans are needed if countries are willing to meet the Paris Agreement goals by the end of the century [8].

The building sector has an important role to play in mitigating climate change. However, in 2019, the sector moved away from contributing to the Paris Agreement goal. CO₂ emissions from the operation of buildings in 2019 increased to their highest level yet at around 10 GtCO₂ or 28% of total global energy-related CO₂ emissions. The final energy consumption of the global buildings sector remained at the same level in 2019 compared to the previous year. The increase in emissions is caused by the continued use of fossil fuels for heating and cooling combined with higher activity levels in regions where electricity remains carbon-intensive. [9]. IEA highlights also growing energy consumption for heating and cooling with rising air-conditioner ownership and extreme weather events as a cause for increasing emissions [10]. Reduction of emissions implies the need for continued efforts to improve energy efficiency and changes in energy production towards more renewable energy sources.

1.3.1 European perspective to climate change and buildings

The building sector is also important for the European Union (EU) in its efforts to reduce emissions and play a vital role in the international community to achieve the goal of the Paris Agreement. Buildings are the single largest energy consumer in Europe. They are responsible for approximately 40% of EU energy consumption and 36% of the greenhouse gas emissions. At present, about 35% of the EU's buildings are over 50 years old, and almost 75% of the building stock is energy inefficient. At the same time, only about 1% of the building stock is renovated each year [11].

1.3.2 Importance of energy efficiency and nearly zero energy building (NZEB)

Buildings are a critical piece of our transition to a lower-carbon future. They are where we live, where we rest, and where we work – and they are responsible for about 40% of global energy consumption and about one-third of global greenhouse gas emissions.

In Europe alone, more than 220 million existing buildings – or 75% of the building stock – are energy-inefficient, with many relying on fossil fuels for heating and cooling. European analysis from our System Value initiative shows that a 20% shift in heating towards heat pump applications running on clean electricity would reduce CO₂ emissions by 9%. Coupled with smart solutions, it could save €3 billion in human health benefits from decreased air pollution between now and 2030. Bear in mind that any building constructed today will be around for the next 50 years or more – so ensuring that new buildings are green and existing buildings are decarbonized, is key to our efforts to combat climate change [12]. The value of reducing energy consumption in buildings has increased worldwide. This is because the consumption of fossil fuels for the full-fledged operations of a building is as high as it is in other industries. Therefore, the adoption of energy efficiency techniques during the construction and operation of buildings would play a crucial role in the creation of sustainable cities in the future.

Energy efficiency is the use of less energy in a building to perform the same operation as buildings that consume energy inefficiently. It should be considered during the design stage, selection of construction materials, construction process, and operation of the building. Adopting passive solar

house design strategies at the design stage is the first step toward an energy-efficient structure. Low-energy building materials and less energy-consuming construction equipment must be used during the construction process. As far as building operation is concerned, utilities for renewable energy systems must be integrated into the building for water heating, photovoltaic electrification, etc.

Efficient energy consumption in buildings is one of the most affordable ways to lessen the detrimental effects of climate change and health-related problems. It reduces household expenses and decreases carbon dioxide emissions. There was a special emphasis on reducing CO₂ emissions at the 26th UN Climate Change Conference of the Parties (COP26) in Glasgow held on 31 October – 13 November 2021.

The concept of NZEB, which is an acronym for the Nearly Zero Energy Building, has been defined in the Energy Performance Directive of Buildings [5] of the European Union legislation. Ukraine as a member of the European Community is willing to implement these solutions to increase the energy efficiency of the Ukrainian building stock. A 'nearly zero-energy building' means a building that has a very high energy performance. The nearly zero or very low amount of energy required should be covered to a very significant extent by energy from renewable sources, including energy from renewable sources produced on-site or nearby"

1.3.3 The importance of NZEB in Ukraine

The current building stock in Ukraine are not energy efficient. It can be assumed that Ukraine will face severe problems with energy supplies, issues with renewable energy integration and higher emission issues in the future. Hence buildings need to be energy efficient.

At present, the two main problems of the development of NZEB buildings in Ukraine are:

- 1) There are no technical requirements for NZEB buildings as requirements for their energy consumption characteristics in Ukraine (e.g., U-values of the walls, window, roof, ventilation heat recovery, on-site renewable production) and,
- 2) The high cost and low affordability of energy efficiency solutions.

To address this issue and concerns in Ukraine, the National Plan is designed in two 5-year time frames . According to the Decree of the Cabinet of Ministry of Ukraine №88-p dated 29/01/2020 On the approval of the Concept of implementation of the state policy in the field of ensuring buildings energy efficiency in terms of increasing the number of nearly zero energy buildings and approval of the National Plan for increasing the number of nearly zero energy buildings¹ [6]. These two 5-year frames are:

- 1) Years 2020-2025 – development of a legal framework, establishment of technical regulations and requirements to the NZEB, setting goals for increasing the number of such buildings and establishing a procedure for monitoring the achievements for set goals.
- 2) Years 2025-2030 – the transition to mandatory compliance with NZEB standards for construction and reconstructed facilities for economic feasibility.

This project is focusing on the first five-year period (2020-2025) of the National Plan delivering the cost-efficient Nearly Zero Energy Building definitions for residential buildings (high-rise apartments) and public buildings (schools and/or kindergartens) to accelerate the development of the technical NZEB regulations in Ukraine and support in developing framework.

¹ <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/88-2020-%D1%80#Text>

1.3.4 Impact of the project and its importance in the current situation

After the start of the Russian invasion of Ukraine that started on 24th February 2022, the importance of the project has increased significantly. This can be observed during conversations with the Ukrainian beneficiary that explained the magnitude of destruction of the buildings and houses that occurred due to the war.

Since the start of the war, the cost of direct damage to Ukraine's infrastructure in the month since Russia invaded the country has reached \$100 billion, according to an analysis from Kyiv School of Economics (KSE) [13].

The beneficiary of the project is the Energy Efficiency Directorate in the Ministry of Communities and Territories Development (MCTD) of Ukraine. This project also provides the Ministry of Communities and Territories Development (MCTD) of Ukraine with a starting point to reconstruct the buildings after the Russian invasion in a better way that can support energy efficiency in the buildings from the beginning. It can assist in developing better building regulations and frameworks that can support and direct the building sector to reach nearly zero energy building targets. The presented solutions in the project are focusing on apartment buildings and school buildings and when these two important building types are reconstructed, such recommendations will be extremely helpful. It can help in two ways, firstly by providing energy-efficient building solutions that will consume less energy and therefore it will lower the investment in energy generation (renewable) plants. Secondly, with cost-optimal building solutions, the investment in the buildings can be lowered as well along with energy efficiency. Therefore, the importance of the project is significant in the local Ukrainian context. Lastly, this project will have a big impact in a way that Ukraine can start the reconstruction of the buildings in an energy efficient manner. The best cost optimal NZEB solutions can be taken in use instead of old practice.

2. Nearly zero energy building concept

According to the EU's 2030 climate and energy framework, the target is to reduce emissions by 55% compared to 1990 levels, increase energy efficiency by 32.5% and increase the share of renewables by 32% [4]. To achieve these targets, buildings must be energy efficient and use a significant amount of locally generated renewable energy. Apart from energy efficiency measures, the flexibility of a building's energy use can assist in reducing operational costs, lower carbon emissions and support the operation of connected energy grids. To avoid curtailing renewable energy sources (RES) when the grid is congested and reduce feed-in tariffs, buildings must be flexible to manage energy consumption, thereby increasing the self-consumption of locally generated energy.

In many districts, cities and regions, buildings are nowadays designed to be nearly zero energy or net zero energy to achieve emission reduction targets and to mitigate climate change [4]. The EU, through the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD), initiated in 2002 [14], adopted in 2006 and updated in 2010 [5] and 2018 [15] and the revised EPBD aims to make all newly-constructed or heavily-renovated buildings adhere to a "nearly zero energy building NZEB" target as of 2021. The policy goal is to decarbonise the whole building stock by 2050.

EPBD (2022) amendment 'zero-emission building' means a building with a very high energy performance, where the very low amount of energy still required is fully covered by energy from renewable sources generated on-site, from a renewable energy community or a district heating and cooling system. 'Nearly zero-energy building' means a building with a very high energy performance, which cannot be lower than the 2023 cost-optimal level and where the nearly zero or very low amount of energy required is covered to a very significant extent by energy from renewable sources, including energy from renewable sources, produced on-site or nearby.

The European EPBD regulation is pushing to improve building efficiency, e.g., by imposing performance measures on new buildings and standardised information provision for existing buildings and the renovation of old buildings (e.g., through information provisions, such as energy performance certificates). The EPBD is a framework at the European level, while the implementation is to be detailed at the member state (MS) level. Procedures, calculations, and definitions differ greatly among EU MS due to local contexts and policy preferences. These calculations are generally based on the ISO EN 52000 series of standards, which defines a framework and calculation methods for assessing the energy performance of buildings [16]. Amongst others, the EPBD requires the construction of NZEB buildings as of 2021 (2019 for new public buildings), but the definition of 'nearly zero energy' is flexible and is to be specified by MS in their adoption of the Directive. MS is required to base the NZEB definitions on a techno-economic optimality analysis, also considering local specificities such as climate and primary energy conversion factors depending on local energy mixes [17,18] and cost. As the assessment of nearly zero energy buildings is at present most often based on calculated performance rather than actual measured data, the definition of the energy flows considered, and the boundary conditions will affect the score. The assessment score can be positively affected if a few energy loads are excluded and considered outside the boundary in the calculations. In this condition, the assessment will present a building to be energy efficient as the total energy consumption will be low. On the other hand, the score can be negatively affected if some energy loads outside the building boundary are included in the calculations, as in this condition, the total energy consumption of the building will increase, and the building will appear to be inefficient and possibly not NZEB. Therefore, identification of energy flows and boundary is important. One of the energy flows which is most often omitted from NZEB definitions is the energy required for charging electric vehicles. Similarly, the nearly or zero energy building concept has received interest at political and international levels. For instance, the United States introduced the Energy Independence and Security Act of 2007 (EISA 2007) to support the building sector to establish zero-energy commercial buildings. Since 2010, new or renovated buildings have had to reduce fossil fuel-based energy consumption by 55% compared to 2003 levels. In addition, from 2030

onwards fossil-based energy consumption will have to be reduced by 100% compared to 2003, thus reaching a zero energy building target [19,20].

Increasing energy efficiency measures, such as using better thermal insulation in the building envelope or more efficient heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) systems, is the first step to apply to reduce overall energy consumption. Next, on-site RES is deployed to deliver energy, thereby reducing carbon emissions. [21]. Solar energy is the biggest RES source in the EU's building sector and can produce emission-free energy both in the form of heat and electricity [22,23]. Traditionally, solar energy is used either to deliver heating energy using a solar thermal (ST) collector or to produce electricity using photovoltaic (PV) panels. A hybrid system known as a photovoltaic-thermal (PV/T) system combines both functions, thus producing both heat and electricity [24]. However, PV is mostly used in buildings because of its ease of installation, maintenance and lower price compared to other technologies [25,26]. Many studies show that the issue with the utilisation of PV is the mismatch between the consumption of the building and the supply of energy from PV in northern and central Europe [27]. For the apartment buildings and high-rise buildings, the roof area available for PV is less compared to total consumption as the habitat density is higher compared to the single-family house. In these areas, electricity from PV is generated during the daytime or during summer, while the building's consumption is high during the evening or in winter, when PV does not produce enough electricity [28]. This issue can be solved by different methods, for instance: the excess energy produced by the photovoltaic can be stored in batteries, converted to heat, sold to the grid, or used to charge electric vehicles (EV) [25].

Amendment of the energy performance of the buildings directive (EPBD) promotes policies that will help to achieve a highly energy-efficient and decarbonised building stock by 2050. According to the EPBD, EU countries must establish long-term renovation strategies to decarbonise the national building stocks by 2050, with indicative milestones for 2030, 2040 and 2050. EPBD also includes provisions for cost-optimal minimum energy performance requirements, nearly zero-energy buildings, energy performance certificates, supporting electro-mobility infrastructure and promoting smart technologies, and introducing an optional European scheme to rating the 'smart readiness' of buildings. [29]

Due to its significant role in energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions, the building sector plays an important role in achieving the EU's targets. Positive energy building PEB is not included explicitly in the legislative framework like NZEB, but it is aligned with the EU's ambitions, targets, and objectives. Most of the material related to NZEBs is relevant also for PEBs. Still, the PEB concept with the two-way exchange with energy grids and the pronounced user-centricity lifts some aspects of the legislation that are not at the core of the NZEB concept.

In this project, the main objectives are to support the development of technical regulations and requirements for cost-efficient NZEB solutions for new apartment buildings and schools in Ukraine and provide these technical recommendations to the Ministry of Development of Communities and Territories of Ukraine

3. State of the art of the new buildings' regulations in Ukraine

The energy consumption of residential buildings in Ukraine is 32% of the total final energy consumption and 11% of CO₂ emissions, which makes them the largest energy consumer in the country [30] by 2019.

Currently, about 66% of residential buildings in Ukraine are older than 50 years, and almost 80% of the residential building stock is inefficient in terms of energy consumption by 2019.

The total area of residential buildings stock in Ukraine is about 968.4 million sq.m., 60% of these areas are in urban settlements by 2019.

At the same time, less than 0.1% of the housing stock is modernized annually in the country. Residential buildings have the highest potential for energy saving – 49.6% of the total energy saving potential in Ukraine. According to different estimates, investment requirements for the complete thermal modernization of the housing stock in Ukraine amount to approx. EUR 45 billion by 2019.

The main problems in improving the energy efficiency of residential buildings in Ukraine are:

- high deterioration of the housing stock and its low energy efficiency at the background of the minimum growth of new buildings.
- significant investment needs for complete thermal modernization of residential buildings.

34.4% of the total number of public buildings in Ukraine belongs to schools [30]. Poor insulated building envelopes and no ventilation cause losses of heating energy and poor indoor air quality. Significant energy conservation potential can be achieved by modernizing ventilation systems, situated in sports halls, assembly halls, swimming pools, and school canteens. Decentralized hot water supply systems using electric water heaters are widely used. The most significant consumers of electricity in schools are the lighting systems.

The Law on Energy Efficiency of buildings (No.2118-VIII) [31] (the Law) was adopted on June 22, 2017, and implemented at the end of July 2018 to meet the requirements of the EPBD Directive. Along with the major state building codes, the Law forms a system of current norms and standards in the field of building energy efficiency (EE) in Ukraine.

Mentioned legislation identifies a set of most important measures to improve EE of buildings and financing tools to support these policies, creates preconditions for the implementation of the national plans to increase the number of Nearly Zero Energy Buildings and regulates the building energy performance certification process. The most important legal and technical documents on buildings EE are presented in *Figure 1*.

Figure 1. The current legislative framework in the field of EE in buildings in Ukraine [32]

As presented in Figure 1 above, some of the existing standards and norms in Ukraine require further development and additional amendments to be fully synchronized with the European Directives, standards, and norms in the area.

The Law “On amendments to some laws of Ukraine regarding the creation of conditions for the introduction of comprehensive thermal modernization of buildings”² was adopted on August 09, 2022, and among other laws amends the Law on Energy Efficiency of buildings. The Law defines NZEB in Ukraine as buildings with a level of EE exceeding the established minimum requirements, in which energy produced with a significant share of renewable energy sources is used to create proper living conditions and/or life activities for people.

Currently, Ukraine is at the stage of revising some norms and standards, as well as transposing the number of European standards (EN) as national standards. However, some important EN standards applicable to the overall energy performance and energy consumption calculation methods (EN 52003), calculation of climate data (EN ISO 15927) and determining indoor environmental parameters (EN 16798), as well as standards applicable to thermal performance calculation methods (EN ISO 13370, EN ISO 12631) have not yet been adopted in Ukraine.

A National Plan³ [6] to increase the number of NZEB has been developed and adopted in 2020. Implementation of the National Plan is expected during 2020-2030 within the following stages:

² The Law on amendments. [Про внесення змін до деяких ... | від 09.07.2022 № 2392-IX \(rada.gov.ua\)](https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/88-2020-%D1%80#Text)

³ <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/88-2020-%D1%80#Text>

- during the first stage (2020-2025) it is planned to implement measures aimed at overcoming technical, organizational, and financial issues by increasing the number of NZEB.
- the second stage (2025-2030) envisages the implementation of measures aimed at implementing the transition to mandatory compliance with the NZEB standards for all construction objects and buildings under reconstruction.

One of the key areas of the National Plan implementation is establishing the obligation of meeting NZEB requirements, which provides for the implementation of several measures, in particular:

- EE of newly constructed buildings must meet the NZEB requirements by December 31, 2027 (completion).
- EE of newly constructed state-owned buildings must meet the NZEB requirements by December 31, 2025.

The following main objectives have been set as intermediate goals:

- Achieving in 2025 a reduction in final energy consumption in the residential sector and public buildings (24% and 16% respectively).
- Reduction by 2025 of final energy consumption in specific indicators and absolute values in the residential sector and public buildings by 1% annually.

Figure 2 shows the overall implementation score on energy efficiency in the building stock. It is observed that the implementation of the energy efficiency, labelling and heating/cooling efficiency in the building has increased from 2020 to 2021. However, this must be further improved to reach the nearly zero energy building level.

Figure 2: Overall electricity efficiency in Ukraine building stock [33].

3.1 Workshops with different stakeholders

Two workshops with the key stakeholders and collaborators and companies were arranged during July 2022 and respectively September 2022 to share information on the on-going project, discuss about the state of the art of the energy regulations and NZEB in Ukraine and to collect the first-hand information on the building design and on the cost.

3.1.1 First workshop

A workshop was held on 14th July 2022 (15:00-17:00) with the local (Ukrainian) stakeholders, arranged by the subcontractor (iC consulenten). The main goal of the workshop was to discuss typical projects for multi-family residential and school types of buildings and general construction principles for the considered types. The participants and companies were as follows:

- Minregion (Ministry of Communities and Territories Development of Ukraine)
- State Agency on Energy Efficiency and Energy Saving of Ukraine
- Association of Energy Auditors of Ukraine
- Design company
- Design and installation company
- Design company and developer
- Architect
- iC consulenten (Consultant)

The main discussion, participants list, and the minutes of the meeting are attached in Annex 1

3.1.2 Second workshop

A workshop was held on 13th September 2022 (14:00-16:00) with the local (Ukrainian) stakeholders, arranged by the subcontractor (iC consulenten). The main goal of the workshop was to discuss dynamics of prices for materials and equipment, approaches to determining the average specific cost of materials and equipment, consideration of additional cost components of materials and equipment and risk assessment. The participants and companies were as follows:

- Minregion (Ministry of Communities and Territories Development of Ukraine)
- State Agency on Energy Efficiency and Energy Saving of Ukraine
- Design and installation company
- Senior researchers
- Supplier of HVAC systems
- Energy suppliers

- NEFCO (CMC for FUTF)
- iC consulenten (Consultant)

The main discussion, participants list and the minutes of the meeting are attached in Annex 2.

3.1.3 Third workshop

The final (third) dissemination workshop and seminar was held on 1st December 2022 (11:00-13:00 Ukrainian time) online. The background of the project, modelling work and final recommendations along with future suggestions were discussed and presented. In total around 100 people and stakeholders (including participants) attended the seminar. The seminar was arranged in two languages for ease of communication (English and Ukrainian). The seminar was opened by the Ministry of Communities and Territories Development (MCTD) of Ukraine. Three polling questions were asked from the stakeholders to initiate the discussions. It was found that the main barriers for implementing energy efficiency (NZEB) projects in the buildings sector are the additional financial support needs, higher investment cost, further support from regulation and policy is need and need of reference projects. It was found that PV, district heating and cooling (with renewables), ground source/air source heat pumps and solar thermal were the main types of renewable energy sources that are preferred in Ukraine climate. It was also identified that most of the stakeholders have limited experience or no previous experience in implementing energy efficiency projects. However, quite a few had a lot of experience as well. Therefore, these findings showed that further support in terms of finance, regulations, demo cases and capacity building is needed in Ukraine while keeping the local climate conditions as centre of planning in terms of renewables.

Moreover, feedback, open questions and answers were also carried out. The feedback about the overall seminar was also send to the stakeholders along with the presentations, recording for their benefit and use. The seminar was recorded. The final presentation, agenda and polls results are attached in the Annex 3.

3.2 Building envelope

Nearly zero-energy requirements (2018) for the building envelope implemented in some Central and Eastern countries are shown in *Table 1*.

Table 1. Nearly zero energy-building requirements in European countries [32].

U-values	Walls (W/m ² ·K)	Roof (W/m ² ·K)	Windows(W/m ² ·K)
Bulgaria	0.22-0.28	0.22-0.25	1.1-1.4
Hungary	0.24	0.17	1.15-1.4
Poland	0.2-0.9	0.15-0.7	0.9-1.4
Slovakia	0.22	0.15	0.85
Czech	0.21	0.17	1.05
Finland	0.17	0.09	1.0

The regulations also establish normative requirements for the building envelope elements. DBN V.2.6-31:2021 [34] “Thermal insulation and energy efficiency of buildings” sets the minimum values of allowed heat resistance coefficients for the enclosing structures $R_{q\text{-min}}$, which can be seen in *Table 2* compared to previous version of the norm. Zone 1 refers to the Northern Zone (Kyiv region) and Zone 2 refers to the Southern Zone (Odesa region).

Table 2. Nearly zero energy-building requirements in Ukraine [32].

Structures	$R_{q\text{ min}}, \text{ m}^2\cdot\text{K}/\text{W}$ ($U = 1/ R_{q\text{ min}}, \text{ W}/\text{m}^2\cdot\text{K}$)			
	Regulations before September 1, 2022		Regulations as of September 1, 2022	
	Zone I	Zone II	Zone I	Zone II
Construction type				
External walls	3.3 (0.303)	2.8 (0.357)	4.0 (0.25)	3.5 (0.286)
Roof (without attic floor)	6.0 (0.167)	5.5 (0.182)	7.0 (0.143)	6.0 (0.167)
Roof (with attic floor)	4.95 (0.202)	4.5 (0.222)	6.0 (0.167)	5.5 (0.182)
Basement ceiling	3.75 (0.267)	3.3 (0.303)	5.0 (0.2)	4.0 (0.25)
Windows	0.75 (1.333)	0.6 (1.667)	0.90 (1.11)	0.70 (1.43)
External doors	0.6 (1.667)	0.5 (2.0)	0.7 (1.429)	0.60 (1.667)

Requirements related to total solar energy transmittances (g-values) for windows are determined neither in current regulation nor in the upcoming norms.

The minimum EE requirements were established by Decree of Ministry of Development of Communities and Territories of Ukraine No: 260, dated 27.10.2020. The minimum requirements for the energy efficiency of buildings for construction objects (newly designed buildings, reconstruction) is to achieve **EE class "C"** [35]. To determine the EE class of a building, the general indicator of specific energy consumption for heating and cooling systems is compared with the EP_p value by using the following formula:

$$\Delta EP = [(EP_{use} - EP_p) / EP_p] \times 100, \text{ where}$$

EP_{use} – General indicator of specific energy consumption for heating and cooling systems obtained by calculation, in accordance with the adopted methodology for determining the EE of buildings;
 EP_p – The maximum allowed value of specific energy consumption for heating and cooling systems (presented in *Table 3* depending on the purpose of the building, its height and temperature zone).

Table 3. Specific energy consumption in Ukraine [32].

EE class of building	$\Delta EP, \%$
A	$\Delta EP < -50$
B	$-50 \leq \Delta EP < -20$
C	$-20 \leq \Delta EP \leq 0$
D	$0 < \Delta EP \leq 20$
E	$20 < \Delta EP \leq 35$
F	$35 < \Delta EP \leq 50$
G	$50 < \Delta EP$

Table 4 presents the maximum allowed specific energy consumption for heating and cooling ($E_{p,p}$ values) for schools and residential buildings set in current regulation for selected types of buildings [35].

Table 4. Specific energy consumption in Ukraine⁴ [35], [32].

Building type	$E_{p,p}$ values, kWh/m ² a [For educational building: kWh/m ³ a]	
	Zone I	Zone II
Residential buildings		
1 to 3-storey buildings	120	110
4 to 9-storey buildings	85	75
10 to 16-storey buildings	75	70
17-storey and higher	70	65
Schools	$[55 \cdot \lambda_{bci} + 24]$	$[52 \cdot \lambda_{bci} + 23]$

3.3 Heating systems for existing buildings

The typical solutions for the heating systems were defined in the first workshop. The main goal of the workshop was to discuss typical projects for multi-family residential and school types of buildings and general construction principles for the considered types. It was discussed that the share of usage of the district and individual heating systems varies by region. Central and Eastern Ukraine (Kyiv, Dnipro, Zaporizhzhia) is dominated by district heating systems, while individual gas

⁴ Decree of Ministry of Development of Communities and Territories of Ukraine No 260 dated 27.10.2020 On the approval of the Minimum requirements for the energy efficiency of buildings

boilers are the main source of heat in western Ukraine. Usually centralized heating or gas heating (boiler) system is used in the apartments and schools.

The required minimum insulation layer thickness (material with thermal conductivity of 0.035 W/(m·K) and temperature difference of 40 °C) is presented in *Table 5*.

The typical technical specifications for tubular foam or rubber pipe insulation are the following:

- Thermal conductivity ratio λ - $\leq 0,042$ W/(m·K).
- Humidity penetration resistance (μ – ratio) ≥ 4.500 .
- Range of operation temperatures t (°C) from -50 to +175

Table 5. Minimum pipeline insulation layer thickness for heat supply, cooling, internal cold supply, and cold and hot water supply (except DHW) according to DBN V.2.5-67:2013 “Heating, ventilation and air conditioning” [32].

No	Pipeline	Minimum insulation layer thickness
1.1	Pipeline with an inner diameter up to 22 mm	20 mm
1.2	Pipeline with an inner diameter from 22 mm to 35 mm	30 mm
1.3	Pipeline with an inner diameter from 35 mm to 100 mm	equal to the inner diameter
1.4	Pipeline with an inner diameter of more than 100 mm	100 mm

3.4 Ventilation systems for existing system

The typical solutions for the ventilation systems were defined in the first workshop.

- At present, the most common ventilation system in residential buildings in Ukraine is natural ventilation [36]. It is not a common practice to implement mechanical ventilation with heat recovery units in the residential sector due to regulatory provisions (separate ducts should be implemented per apartment due to fire safety issues). However, it is highly recommended by stakeholders to develop a model considering individual or centralized mechanical ventilation systems with heat recovery units for residential buildings in case of cost-effectiveness of such solution.
- For schools, it is a common practice to use mechanical exhaust for premises such as gym, assembly halls etc, while it is also needed in classes. Thus, it is also highly recommended by stakeholders to foresee such a system for the classes in schools.

In apartment buildings, the normal configuration is based on natural ventilation extraction is carried out through the internal wall ventilation ducts built into the kitchens and bathrooms, which are made of ready-made blocks.

Air inflow is carried out due to infiltration through leaks through the building envelope. For ventilation of non-residential premises, separate ventilation ducts are provided, which are supposed to be laid out of brick in the wall structure.

While implementation of a mechanical ventilation system with heat recovery is not mandatory under the norms, the introduction of such systems must comply with the established minimum heat recovery efficiency coefficient established in the Ukrainian standards, as presented in *Table 6*.

Table 6. Minimum efficiency of ventilation heat recovery in school buildings as per DBN V.2.5-67:2013 “Heating, ventilation and air conditioning” [32].

Number of working hours per year	Minimum heat recovery efficiency coefficient				
	Outdoor air flow rate, m ³ /s				
	from 0.55 to 1.39	from 1.39 to 2.78	from 2.78 to 6.94	from 6.94 to 13.89	more 13.89
Less than 2000	-	0.40	0.43	0.50	0.55
From 2000 to 4000	0.40	0.43	0.47	0.53	0.58
From 4000 to 6000	0.43	0.45	0.50	0.58	0.60
More than 6000	0.45	0.50	0.55	0.63	0.68

The maximum allowed values of specific fan power, depending on the system type, which must be observed for projects with mechanical ventilation provided, are presented in *Table 7*.

Table 7. Specific ventilation capacity as per DBN V.2.5-67:2013 “Heating, ventilation and air conditioning” [32].

Application	Specific ventilation capacity P_{SFP} , W/(m ³ /s)
Supply fan:	2000-3000
– air conditioning system;	
– ventilation system without heat utilization	1250-2000
Exhaust fan:	2000-3000
– air conditioning system or ventilation system with heat utilization;	
– ventilation system without heat utilization	1250-2000

3.5 Centralized energy systems for buildings

Based on the data of MinRegion [37] centralized heat supply covers approx. 38% of the households. In individual heating systems, the largest share of generation uses natural gas (74%) for heating, followed by coal (11%), firewood for heating (9%) and other solid fuels. Natural gas is used for heating in 6.59 million households, while district heating is used in 5.49 million households, followed by 2.26 million households with other heat sources. Figure 8 shows the

energy mix of energy sources used for heating for each region in Ukraine, but also Ukraine in general, as of 2016. There is no updated information on the distribution of heat sources, however, no major changes have been observed.

The share of usage of district heating systems varies by region. As can be seen in *Figure 3*, central and eastern Ukraine (Kyiv, Dnipro, Zaporizhzhia) is dominated by district heating systems, while individual gas boilers are the main source of heat in western Ukraine.

Figure 3: Energy generation and distribution in Ukraine [32].

Adopted in Ukraine primary energy (PEF) and GHG emission factors for different energy sources⁵, are shown in Table 8.

Table 8. Primary Energy Factors and GHG emission factors for selected fuels as per the Decree of Ministry of Regional Development, Construction and Housing and Utilities of Ukraine No: 169, dated 11.07.2018 [32], [37]

Energy Carrier	Primary energy factors (PEF)	GHG emission factors (gCO ₂ /kWh)
Biofuel (solid)	1.2	40
Biofuel (gas)	1.4	100
Coal	1.1	360
Natural gas	1.1	220
Electricity	2.5	420
District Heating and Cooling	1.3	260

⁵The Ministry of Regional Development, Construction, Housing and Communal Services of Ukraine. Heating in housing and utilities sector: Status and Prospects. Document for discussion. https://www.minregion.gov.ua/wp-content/uploads/2016/04/Heating-in-housing-and-utilities-sector_25.03.2016.pdf

3.5.1 Photovoltaic

Due to the legislation, two types of photovoltaic plants are widely used in Ukraine: bigger commercial solar power plants installed in the fields and small solar power plants (up to 30 kWp of AC power) for single-family residential buildings. These plants have the right to supply excess electricity generation to the grid using the feed-in tariff or auction scheme. Also, industrial, and commercial buildings are installing roof-based PV systems as compensation for their use and without feed-in to the grid. The installed power of the PV system is calculated in such a manner that down-regulation at the feed-in point is kept to a minimum.

There is a need for further development of the regulation to exploit the potential of roof-based PV systems for residential and public buildings. Some discussions on the implementation of net metering or net billing approach are held in Ukraine (Draft Law of Ukraine “On the introduction of amendments to some laws of Ukraine regarding the improvement of the conditions for supporting the production of electricity from renewable energy sources by generating plants of consumers”)⁶. This will allow to implement net metering for apartments and residential houses. This approach will allow the users to feed in the excess energy to the grid.

At this moment two types of systems can be considered for residential and school buildings: roof-based PV systems for compensation for their use and without feed-in to the grid without and with accumulators. Façade based PV can also be examined in future studies.

3.5.2 Solar thermal energy

Solar thermal is a technology for harnessing solar energy for thermal energy (heat). Solar thermal systems are used in Ukraine either to compensate energy consumption of DHW preparation or for pool heating. These systems are typically implemented in single-family residential buildings or projects with higher consumption for DHW.

Solar thermal collectors can be classified as Low-, medium- or High-temperature collectors. For swimming pools and low temperature application flat-plates collectors can be used, for instance in schools. Flat plate collectors can be used also for medium-temperature application such as it can be used for heating water or air for residential and commercial use [38]. The main types of solar thermal collectors used in the market are evacuated tube solar thermal collector and flat plate collectors. The evacuated tubes are energy efficient (70%) and flat plate collectors can reach around 20-30% [39]. Flat plate collectors are widely used due to lower costs.

Solar thermal systems can be implemented in the buildings to collect heat energy from sun as renewable energy and this heat can be used to provide heating to the buildings. The technical integration of solar thermal systems for multi-family residential buildings is technically possible (especially if the building is equipped with a roof-based or free-standing boiler plant). The heat energy produced by the collectors can be used directly for space heating and DHW application. Moreover the technical system for solar thermal collector also need tanks that can act as buffer storage and allows storage of heat energy for use during night and winters. It needs additional piping, pumps and space to install such systems in the building. Experts are also needed to building and install such systems on the buildings as high temperature is produced on site. The main problem with the implementation of a solar thermal system in school buildings is that the period of maximum energy available from solar radiation coincides with low or no DHW

⁶ <https://www.mev.gov.ua/rehulyatornyy-akt/pro-vnesennya-zmin-do-deyakykh-zakoniv-ukrayiny-shchodo-udoskonalennya-umov>

consumption during summer holidays. Therefore, it can be used for swimming pool heating or heat can be stored in tanks and pools in schools. The average cost of the solar thermal system is around 2100 €/kWh [40] and this is expensive compared to the PV system. This technology is not studied in the project and it can be studied in a separate project in details for its feasibility in Ukraine.

3.5.3 Biomass

Biomass is considered a sustainable energy source if the amount of biomass used to produce energy is the same as the amount of biomass grown to replace the consumed biomass. The emissions are produced in form of carbon dioxide when biomass is used for energy production. The EU Renewable energy directive (RED II) defines the sustainability criteria for biomass use with the 20 MW threshold of energy production [41]. Biomass is a popular energy source because it is flexible. It can be transported to various locations and stored [41]. Most biomass is used as a replacement for fossil fuel, and it is used to produce district heating and cooling (e.g. in Finland) [42]. In the EU, most of the biomass is produced in the forest. The forest biomass is used to produce chips and wood pellets that are used in the CHPs for heat and electricity generation [42]. Biomass use can provide energy independence, local economic development and to some extent carbon neutrality.

Since a major part of energy consumption in buildings in Ukraine is associated with heating. Biomass or biogas boilers may have the highest potential for renewable energy use. Small biomass boilers are being implemented in single-family houses and bigger ones are used for district heating boiler plants. Since some of the schools in Ukraine are connected to their gas boiler station a switch to biomass boilers might be possible. It is important to note that biomass may not be feasible at the building level in general, especially if the building is in a densely populated area due to the logistic issues and emissions caused by the burning process of biomass. In this project, biomass is not considered as heating and energy source due to the limited application of biomass at building level.

In Ukraine, the use of solid fuel boilers on biomass is widespread, but in most cases we are talking about the use of firewood, wood production waste, combustible waste, etc. In a considerable number of cases, these are low-tech boilers that are fundamentally different from similar devices used in developed European countries and meet high standards for environmental friendliness and efficiency. In order to contribute to the positive CO₂ balance, it is important to keep the transportation distances as short as possible. In addition, in Ukraine, unfortunately, there are no state mechanisms for ensuring the restoration of forests used to produce fuel resulting in sustainability issues. Thus, the practice of using solid fuel boilers in Ukraine and replacing gas boilers with them has several peculiarities and cannot be fully considered as renewable energy source. Some other challenges are the local market is underdeveloped, low investments, lack of incentives, complicated access to heating network, handling of biomass, source limitations etc. [43]. Therefore all these issues has to be addressed. The safe burning process and maintenance of the biomass-based power plants add to the investment costs. The average cost of the biomass system is around 2200 €/kWh [40]. Another challenge with biomass is the limited availability of reliable, affordable, and sustainable biomass in Ukraine. It is essential to consider the life cycle emissions for biomass and the source of the biomass has been identified to be sure that it is sustainable and carbon neutral. This technology is not studied in the project, and it can be studied in a separate project in details for its feasibility in Ukraine.

3.5.4 Geothermal energy (heat pumps)

Heat pumps are also gaining popularity in terms of their utilisation as a renewable energy source to provide clean heating and cooling energy at the building level. For instance, in Finland, more than one million heat pumps are installed with up to 7 billion USD that provides clean, combustion-

beyond the obvious

free heating and cooling energy to the houses. This encourages building owners, public buildings etc. to replace oil heating boilers and the direct electric heating system needed to heat the houses during freezing winters [44]. The use of ground source heat pumps for space heating and cooling as well as for domestic hot water is promising for Ukraine. There are several commercial and public buildings [45] (including a full-scale private school) that have implemented ground source heat pumps. This type of heat pump has a higher seasonal coefficient of performance (SCOP) value and lower dependency of efficiency and heating output on the outside air temperatures. Based on the heat source (e.g. ground, water, air) and the transfer media (air or water) there are a wide variety of heat pumps available. Usually ground source heat pumps has higher performance. Ground source (or geothermal) heat pumps are divided by the orientation of the pipes to vertical and horizontal systems and to shallow (typically 100–300 m) or deep (typically up to 600–800 m) according to the depth of the wells in vertical systems [46]. Different heat-pump applications are among the most suitable renewable technologies for building level. The operation of heat pumps requires electricity, and that should ideally come from renewable sources to fulfil the status as

The FUTF has implemented ground source heat pump project for the student dormitory in Rivne with the local technical university (NUWEE) [45]. Heat pumps can be used along with district heating in Ukraine to decarbonize the heating network and provide renewable based energy to the buildings. This will support Ukrainian building stock to be energy efficient and reach NZEB levels using higher COP of heat pumps and better utilization of renewable energy and storage [42]. Heat pump requires drilling technology for boreholes drilling and deeper boreholes could provide better performance. Moreover, the heating network, piping, tanks, boreholes and controls in the building in Ukraine must be designed so it can integrate heat pumps. Space for installing such systems in buildings must be planned as well especially in cities where space is limited. The average investment cost for the ground source heat pump is around 1000–1200 €/kW for building application [47]. This can be studied in a separate study where application and feasibility of heat pumps integrated with the buildings can be analysed.

4. Climatic conditions in Ukraine

In Ukraine, existing norms establish requirements for both specific energy consumption indicators and the envelope elements (walls, roofs, basement ceilings, windows, and doors) based on climate data. Ukraine is split into two climate zones, distinguished only through the number of heating degree days to account for climate differences in the country, as shown in *Figure 4*.

Figure 4: Map of climate zones of Ukraine DBN V.2.6-31: 2021.

As Ukrainian norms are using the monthly quasi-stationary method for calculating energy need and energy consumption for heating and cooling the normative climatic data is also presented for the monthly time intervals. Available climatic data for different locations in Ukraine include the following: outside air temperatures, wind speed and direction, solar radiation data, relative humidity, precipitation etc.

For the hourly simulations conducted in this study, ASHRAE IWE C 2 (International Weather for Energy Calculations) weather data for Kyiv and Odesa was used. Figure 5 below shows the annual temperature profile for both locations. According to the data, annual average temperature is 8.7 °C for Kyiv, and 10.9 °C for Odesa. There are also other climatic differences between the locations, with Odesa having higher air humidity and solar irradiance. Figure 5 displays the hourly outdoor temperature for both climate zones.

Figure 5: Hourly ambient air-dry bulb temperature in Kyiv and Odesa according to ASHRAE IWE C 2.

Heating degree days and cooling degree days for the temperature data of each climate zone was also calculated, using the method described by Eurostat [48]. *Table 9* displays the results.

Table 9. Mean temperatures, heating degree days and cooling degree days for the climate zones for 2019.

	Zone 1 (Kyiv)	Zone 2 (Odesa)	South Europe (Sofia) ⁷	North Europe (Helsinki) ⁸
Annual mean temperature [°C]	8.7	10.9	10.1	6.1
Heating degree days	3569	3019	2488	3831
Cooling degree days	27	139	180	0

5. Technical and cost data for simulation

5.1 The state-of-the-art building

According to the State Agency on Energy Efficiency and Energy Saving of Ukraine (SAEE) [49] which maintains the database of energy performance certificates (EPCs), there are 1314 residential multi-family buildings and 65 educational facilities that have an energy performance certificate.

The typical area for the residential buildings is around 4000 -6000 m² (around 314 buildings) and the number of floors is around 9-10 floors (118 buildings). Similar heated areas (5419 m²) and floor height (9 floors) were found in the building construction from 1978-1988 [30].

For the educational buildings, the typical area for educational buildings is around 1000m² - 3000 m² (around 22 buildings) and the number of the floor is around 1-2 floors (15 buildings). Similar heated area (1312 m²) and floor height (2 floors) was found in the building construction from 1978-1988 [50].

Based on the statistics [49] and suggested by the stakeholders in the workshop it is decided to use (10000 m²) (heated area) and 10 floors for the residential building, equalling to around 200 apartments and 700 tenants, and (10000~13000 m²) (heated area) and 3 floors of the school building in the calculations.

⁷ <https://energy.at-site.be/pvgis/EU/Sofia/?menu=3>

⁸ https://en.ilmatieteenlaitos.fi/heating-degree-days?7r87D3pXt5h3S3AkDpM0uF_q=y%253D2021

The case studies and two building type that will be simulated are shown in *Table 10*.

Table 10. Case studies

	New multi-story apartment (one case*)	New School or Kindergarten (one case*)
Reference case Business as usual (BAU), no RES; in accordance with legislation and state building codes	R** value (floor, roof, walls), R value (windows), HVAC system, heating/cooling set points	R value (floor, roof, walls), R value (windows), HVAC system, heating/cooling set points
25% improvement in BAU, no RES	R value (floor, roof, walls), R value (windows), HVAC system	R value (floor, roof, walls), R value (windows), HVAC system
50% improvement in BAU, no RES	R value (floor, roof, walls), R value (windows), HVAC system	R value (floor, roof, walls), R value (windows), HVAC system
50% improvement in BAU, with onsite RES	R value (floor, roof, walls), R value (windows), HVAC system	R value (floor, roof, walls), R value (windows), HVAC system

**One case means that the simulation study will be done for one typical building size and shape. The technology options or measures will be varied according to the table.*

***Thermal resistance R-value (unit m^2K/W) is generally used in Ukraine; Thermal transmittance U-value (unit W/m^2K) is generally used in European approaches and $U=1/R$.*

5.2 About the simulation software - IDA ICE

IDA Indoor Climate and Energy (IDA ICE) is a new type of simulation tool that takes building performance to another level. It accurately models the building, its systems, and controllers – ensuring the lowest possible energy consumption and the best possible occupant comfort. IDA ICE is an innovative and trusted whole-year detailed and dynamic multi-zone simulation application for the study of thermal indoor climate as well as the energy consumption of the entire building. The physical models of IDA ICE reflect the latest research and best models available, and the computed results compare well with measured data. While serving a global market, IDA ICE is adapted to local languages and requirements (climate data, standards, special systems, special reports, product, and material data). *Figure 6* shows the simulation platform of the IDA-ICE software [51].

Figure 6. (Source: IDA-ICE, <https://www.equa.se/en/ida-ice>) [51].

Some of the key functionalities of IDA-ICE are:

- “Usability - The IDA ICE user interface is designed to make it easy to build and simulate both simple and advanced cases, while still offering the advanced user full flexibility. You can refine your model in steps, while always providing both 3D graphical and tabular feedback. You work in a single program and may jump back and forth between tasks [51].”
- “Productivity - Productivity tools like BIM import and version handling make you more efficient. IDA ICE imports all common 2D and 3D CAD files, and it supports IFC models generated by, e.g. ArchiCAD, Revit, AutoCAD Architecture, and MagiCAD [51].”
- “Flexibility - Equation-based modelling, using the Modelica-like Neutral Model Format (NMF), makes it straightforward to quickly expand the software with new modelling capabilities, either by our in-house development team or by the experienced user. The newly created component models can also easily be shared with other IDA ICE users [51].”
- “Quality - An advantage of using a modern general-purpose variable time step solver, rather than the hand-coded component subroutines of all other available whole-building simulators, is that it automatically adapts to the nature of the problem. By choice of tolerance parameters, you can effectively eliminate numerical errors and see how the equations truly behave – even with a time resolution of seconds if needed [51].”

5.3 Domestic hot water supply

According to regulatory requirements DSTU B A.2.2-12:2015 “Energy efficiency of buildings. Method of calculating energy consumption for heating, cooling, ventilation, lighting, and hot water supply”⁹, it is allowed to use specific energy consumption for DHW per 1 m² of conditioned building area for energy efficiency certification, as specified in Table 11. For the apartment

⁹ DSTU B A.2.2-12:2015. http://online.budstandart.com/ua/catalog/doc-page.html?id_doc=61634

building, the value of 20 kWh/m² is suggested according to the Ukrainian standard, however to simulate realistically and not to underestimate the calculations, the value suggested by Finnish building code [52] [53] was used.

Table 11. Annual DHW energy consumption for the selected building types as per DSTU B A.2.2-12:2015 “Energy efficiency of buildings. Method of calculating energy consumption for heating, cooling, ventilation, lighting, and hot water supply” [54], [32].

Building type	Energy needs for DHW
Multi-apartment residential buildings	35 kWh/m ² (36 l/occupant/day) *
Educational buildings	10 kWh/m ²

*Assuming 22 m² of living area per occupant

5.4 Airtightness

Table 12 presents the normative values of n₅₀ air exchange rate (infiltration) for different EE classes in Ukraine According to standard DSTU B.V.2.6-189 “Methods of selection of material for insulation of buildings”. It should be noted that this is the previous version of DBN “Thermal insulation of buildings”, and the new version does not include these requirements.

Table 12. Airtightness parameter n₅₀ for different energy efficiency classes in Ukraine [32].

Building type	Building	n ₅₀
	EE class	hour ⁻¹
Residential, administrative, educational, and medical buildings	C	2.0
	B	1.5
	A	0.8
Public buildings other than the abovementioned	C	2.0
	B	1.5
	A	1.0

Values of n₅₀ give the air change rate at the pressure difference of 50 pascal. In simulation, these values are converted to actual infiltration air change rate using the following equation defined in Finnish building code [52] [53], since the Ukrainian standard does not specify a method for estimation of the infiltration flow rate:

$$n = \frac{n_{50}}{X} [1/h],$$

where n₅₀ is infiltration flow rate at 50 Pascal pressure difference (Table 12) [1/h],

X is a constant for converting n₅₀ to normal operating pressure difference.

The proper value of X, and thereby the actual air change rate, depends on building height. In this case, values as per the Finnish building code [52] [53] were used (Table 13),

Table 13. Airtightness parameter.

Number of floors (floor height ~3 m)	X
1	35
2	24
3 - 4	20
5 -	15

5.5 Losses

Heating system losses are calculated separately for heat generation (DH substation), distribution (pipelines within the building), and emission (heating room units). Generation and emission losses are assumed as unrecoverable, distribution losses have recoverable and unrecoverable parts. Figure 7 visualizes the components of heating system losses.

Figure 7. Visualization of the components of heating system losses.

Cooling system losses are assumed to be incorporated into AC unit EER (energy efficiency ratio)

5.6 Cooling

Currently, it is not a common practice to implement centralized air conditioning systems in Ukraine for the considered types of buildings, however decentralized split air conditioners can be used for cooling purposes for both residential buildings and schools. For newly constructed schools it can be also proposed to use either a Variable Refrigerant Flow or a Chiller for cooling purposes.

For the apartment buildings decentralized air condition units can be used, however it can be upgraded to centralized units that can provide cooling to the apartment for higher performance and energy saving. Cooling system can also be integrated with the ventilation systems in the building if ventilation units are used that can provide cool air. This can improve the overall indoor environment.

If using a centralized heat pump for heating of a building, the same heat pump can be operated in reverse during summer. This is effective use of equipment, since it eliminates the need for individual cooling units in the apartments.

District cooling is also another recommended option that can be integrated with the buildings (like district heating). The district heating and cooling network can be coupled via heat pumps systems that can provide heating during winters and cooling during summers to the buildings. This can also help in recovering waste heat on district/city level, and improve the overall performance of NZEB building (by reducing the overall energy consumption)

Similarly, for school buildings, district cooling network or centralized chiller units can be used instead of decentralized units. The overall cooling consumption of the buildings can be reduced through passive methods that is by controlling the opening of the windows during summers (using free cooling) and by using fixed and moveable shadings.

5.7 Unoccupied period

Default values for number of holidays are provided for each month in *Table 14* and this is considered while simulating the case of the school building.

Table 14. Unoccupied period (number of holidays per month) in the simulations [32].

Building type	Number of holidays per month											
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Residential	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Schools	3	-	1	1	3	1	22	22	-	-	-	-

5.8 Conventional input data related to activity data

Internal temperatures, duration of the heating and cooling periods and other default values for selected types of buildings are provided in *Table 15*.

Table 15. Default values related to activity data, according to DSTU B A.2.2-12:2015 “Energy efficiency of buildings. Method of calculating energy consumption for heating, cooling, ventilation, lighting, and hot water supply” [32].

Input data	Multi-family residential buildings	Schools
<u>Occupancy</u>		
Gross area per person, m²/person	40	10
<u>Values of set-point, reduced set-point, and corrected temperature</u>		
Internal set-point* temperature for heating, °C (Occupied period)	20	20
Internal set-back** temperature for heating, °C	17	17

(Unoccupied periods)			
Internal corrected*** set-point temperature for heating, °C		19	19
Operation schedule of heating, hours per week		112	50
Internal set-point temperature for cooling, °C		26	24
Internal set-back temperature for cooling, °C		26	27
Internal corrected set-point temperature for cooling, °C		26	25
Schedule of cooling, hours per week		112	50
<u>Heat flow rate from occupants, lighting system and appliances</u>			
Average heat flow per person, W/person		70	70
Schedule of use, hours per week****		112	50
Metabolic heat from occupants, W/m²		1.8	7.0
Heat gains from lighting, W/m²		2.0	7.0
Heat gains from appliances, W/m²		2.0	6.0

* Internal temperature during occupied period.

** internal temperature during unoccupied period.

***corrected internal temperature for the whole period.

****for internal heat gains calculation (metabolic, lighting, appliances)

The estimated indoor air temperatures for heating system design and requirements for air exchange rate for residential buildings are presented in *Table 16*¹⁰:

Table 16. Estimated indoor air temperatures for heating system design and requirements for air exchange in the spaces as per DBN B.2.2-15: 2019 “Buildings and structures - Residential buildings” [32].

Space type	Estimated indoor air temperature, °C	Minimum air exchange rate for heat losses calculation, hour ⁻¹		Minimum air exchange rate for equipment and air ducts selection
		Mechanical ventilation	Natural ventilation	
Living room, bedroom, children's room, cabinet	22 ± 2	0.5	0.5	0.6 hour ⁻¹
Kitchen, kitchen-dining room	-	-	1.5	72 m ³ /hour or 60 m ³ /hour ¹⁾
with a size of not more than 20 m ³	19.5 ± 3	1.0		
with a size of more than 20 m ³	19.5 ± 3	0.5		
Bathroom	25 ± 1.5 ²⁾	0.5	1.5	54 m ³ /hour
Toilet	22 ± 2	0.5	1.5	36 m ³ /hour
Combined bathroom	25 ± 1.5 ²⁾	0.5	1.5	90 m ³ /hour
Lobby, common corridor, stairwell, hallway of the apartment	19.5 ± 4	-		-
Premises for duty staff	22 ± 2	0.5		0.5 hour ⁻¹
Smoke-free stairwell	14 ³⁾	-		-
Elevator engine room	5 ⁴⁾	-		0.5 hour ⁻¹
Garbage collection chamber, premise	5	-		1 hour ⁻¹
Heated parking garage	5	-		By calculation
Switchboard room	5	-		0.5 hour ⁻¹
1) In kitchens with electric stoves.				

¹⁰ DBN B.2.2-15: 2019 Buildings and structures. Residential buildings. Substantive provisions. https://www.minregion.gov.ua/wp-content/uploads/2019/08/IB_8-19.pdf

Note 1: In heat and technological calculations of premise enclosures relative humidity of 55% is accepted

Note 2: Values of the air exchange rate are attributed to the internal volume of the room

Note 3: During the warm period of the year when using the cooling or air conditioning system, the estimated resulting premise temperature is taken as 24.5 ± 1.5

Note 4: Consumption and air exchange rate for premises is indicated for premises without equipment in which combustion takes place (fireplace, boiler, gas column)

Table 17 presents the required indoor air temperature and air exchange rate for typical premises in school building.

Table 17. Required indoor air temperature and air exchange rate for typical spaces in school building [32].

Space type	Design air temperature, °C	Air exchange requirements (hour ⁻¹)	
		supply	exhaust
Classrooms, training offices and laboratories of secondary education institutions	18	16 m ³ /hour per capita	
Primary school classrooms	20	16 m ³ /hour per capita	
Informatics and Computer Science classroom	20	(3)	(3)
Auditoriums, classrooms in vocational schools and higher education institutions, training workshops with areas for theoretical classes, reading rooms, halls for course design, painting, drawing and sculpture studio, assembly hall, singing and music classrooms	18	20 m ³ /hour per capita	
Sports halls, choreography studio	18	By calculation, but not more than 80 m ³ /hour per capita	
Swimming pool hall for learning to swim	30	By calculation	
Swimming pool of educational and training swimming	27	By calculation	
Teacher's room, club rooms	18	(1.5), but not more than 20 m ³ /hour of outdoor air per capita	
Administration offices, public organizations` rooms, rest rooms, offices of speech therapist, psychologist, sociologist, library (except reading room)	18	(1), but not more than 20 m ³ /hour of outdoor air per capita	
Doctor's office (medical room)	22	(1.5), but not more than 20 m ³ /hour of outdoor air per capita	
Shower rooms	25	-	(5)
Locker rooms:			
a) by sports halls;	22	-	(1.5)
b) by showers	23	In the volume of showers` exhaust	
Toilets and washbasins	20	-	50 m ³ per 1 toilet 25 m ³ per 1 urinal

Bedrooms of primary school students	19	(1.5), but not more than 16 m ³ /hour of outdoor air per capita	
Educational laboratories (except that of school)	18	By calculation according to ToR	
Laboratory utensils washing units without fume hoods	18	(4)	(6)
Lobbies and recreation area	16	-	-
Dressing rooms	16	-	(1.5)
Canteen:			
a) hot shop;	5 (out of hours)	By calculation	
b) shops: cold, cooking, meat, fish, vegetables;	16	(3)	(4)
c) washing dishes room;	20	(4)	(6)
d) vegetable pantry;	5	-	(2)
e) dry food pantry;	12	-	(2)
f) loading and packing room;	16	-	-
g) dining room	16	By calculation	
Cinema room	16	By the volume of the exhaust from the movie projectors	
Photo laboratory, film and photo laboratory, technical centre	18	-	(2)
Mini-zoo/"living corner"	20	-	(5)

5.9 Auxiliary electricity consumption

For building auxiliary electricity consumption (electricity use by HVAC systems) values suggested by Finnish building energy certificate guide [52] [53] (Table 18) are used:

Table 18. Components of auxiliary electricity consumption

Heating system pumping	0.228 W/m ²
DH substation	0.008 W/m ²
DHW pumping	0.019 W/m ²
Ventilation specific fan power*	1.8 kW/m ³

*For cases with mechanical supply and return ventilation

5.10 Energy prices

This chapter presents the findings on tariffs for heat energy, electrical energy, natural gas, and cold water used in residential and school buildings. All tariffs presented below in Table 19 include VAT (valid as of beginning of 2022).

Table 19. Energy and resources tariffs for residential and school buildings in selected regions in Ukraine

Energy and water resources	Kyiv region		Odesa region	
	Residential buildings	Schools	Residential buildings	Schools

Heating energy [EUR/kWh]	0.05 ¹¹	0.10 ¹²	0.06 ¹³	0.11 ¹⁴
DHW [EUR/m³]	3.32 ¹⁵	5.54 ¹⁶	Not supplied ¹⁷	
Electrical energy [EUR/kWh]	0.06 ¹⁸	0.15 ¹⁹	0.06 ²⁰	0.21*
Natural gas [EUR/m³]	0.29 ²¹		0.27 ²²	
Cold water [EUR/m³]	1.03 ²³		1.19 ²⁴	

*Based on the information from our colleagues in Odesa

The interest rate of 8% is assumed based on the National bank of Ukraine (before war) [25], [55]. A 25% interest rate is also assumed for one case to show the impact of increase in the interest rate Ukraine [55] (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Interest rate development in Ukraine [55].

¹¹ <https://index.minfin.com.ua/ua/tariff/Kyiv/hotwater/>

¹² https://kyivcity.gov.ua/npa/pro_vnesennya_zmin_do_rozporядzhennya_vikonavchogo_organu_kivsko_misko_radi_kivsko_misko_derzhavno_administratsi_vid_13_zhovtnya_2021_roku__2145/kmva__510/

¹³ <https://www.teplo.od.ua/2021/10/20/tarifi/>

¹⁴ <https://www.teplo.od.ua/2021/10/20/tarifi/>

¹⁵ <https://index.minfin.com.ua/ua/tariff/Kyiv/hotwater/>

¹⁶ https://kyivcity.gov.ua/npa/pro_vnesennya_zmin_do_rozporядzhennya_vikonavchogo_organu_kivsko_misko_radi_kivsko_misko_derzhavno_administratsi_vid_13_zhovtnya_2021_roku__2145/kmva__510/

¹⁷ <https://spilka.pro/v-odesi-vidmovlysya-vid-garyachoyi-vody/>

¹⁸ <https://index.minfin.com.ua/ua/tariff/electric/>

¹⁹ <https://koec.com.ua/page?root=23>

²⁰ <https://index.minfin.com.ua/ua/tariff/electric/>

²¹ <https://index.minfin.com.ua/tariff/gas/Kyiv/>

²² <https://index.minfin.com.ua/tariff/gas/odessa/>

²³ <https://vodokanal.Kyiv.ua/rozrakhunki-%D1%96-tarifi>

²⁴ <https://index.minfin.com.ua/ua/tariff/water/odessa/>

6. Multi-story apartment building analysis

6.1 Model description

The modelled apartment building is based on drawings of a two-staircase-building, consisting of ground floor/basement with offices or stores, 9 floors of apartments, and a topmost technical floor (Figure 9). The number of apartments in floors 1-9 is 144, and total number of apartments is 160 including the separate commercial properties of the ground floor. The technical floor is modelled as unheated; top insulation is placed in the ceiling between the 9th floor and the technical floor. Apartment floors 1-8 are modelled as a duplicated single floor since they are practically identical in design. Total heated area is 10900 m², and total area (with the technical floor included) is 12000 m².

Figure 9. Apartment building model in IDA-ICE.

Spaces within the building are separated to apartment level zones, as per EN ISO 13790 (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Floor plan of floors 1 – 9 in IDA-ICE.

6.1.1 Input parameters

Table 20 is a summary of model input parameters relevant to the energy simulation.

Table 20. Apartment building model input parameters

Geometry	Windows	Ventilation	Heating system	Cooling system	Internal gains [*]
Volume 35400 m ³	Window area 1865 m ²	Natural ventilation with no heat recovery (simulated as mechanical exhaust with zero fan power)	District heating Setpoint 20 °C	Cooling based on apartment-level AC units	Heat from occupants 1.8 W/m ²
Envelope area 8200 m ²	Portion of envelope 22.7 %	Ventilation flow rate (constant flow, always on): 0.55 L/s/m ² (ACH: 0.61 1/h)	Generation efficiency 96 %	Setpoint 26 °C	Heat from lighting 2 W/m ²
External wall area 4060 m ²	Portion of vertical envelope area 31.4 %		Radiator emission efficiency 98 %	EER = 3	Heat from equipment 2 W/m ²
Roof area 1130 m ²		Infiltration flow rate: n ₅₀ = 2.0 1/h, n = 0.13 1/h	Distribution efficiency based on building geometry	Losses incorporated into the EER	Percentage of usage 66 %*
Total floor area 12000 m ²					
Heated floor area 10900 m ²					
Ground area 1140 m ²					

* From standardized schedule of use for multi-family residential buildings (table 15) Number of use hours is 112 hours per week, but norms for schedule are not available, therefore the internal loads are divided by 112/168=0.66.

Two versions of the building model were created, for Kyiv and Odesa climate zones. Table 21 includes the structures and U-values for the default version of the building in both the climate zones. The structures are based on the information available in the received drawings, with the insulation thickness modified so that the U-values correspond with the latest regulations (Table 2).

Table 21. Apartment building model default version building structures, and U-values for external constructions.

Structure	Materials	U-value, Kyiv [W/m ² K]	U-value, Odesa [W/m ² K]
External walls	Heavy brick Air gap Insulation Light brick	0.25	0.29

	Sand and cement plaster		
9 th floor ceiling	Sand and cement screed	0.17	0.18
	Insulation		
	Concrete		
Roof	Insulation	0.36	0.36
	Expanded clay		
	Concrete		
External floor	Concrete	0.2	0.25
	Polystyrene		
Windows	2-chamber double-glazed (4i-10-4M1-10-4i)	1.11	1.43
Internal floors	Sand and cement screed	-	-
	Concrete		
Internal walls	Light brick	-	-

Thermal bridges of structures are included in the minimum U-values presented by regulations, and therefore they are not separately included. In this study, it is assumed that for the improved insulation U-values, thermal bridges are similar to the default case.

The table below (Table 22) includes the losses figures used in the apartment building model, as explained in chapter 5.5 and based on the typical case calculations in Ukraine.

Table 22. Heating system & DHW losses of apartment building model, with default parameters.

Loss type	Value (Kyiv climate zone)	Value (Odesa climate zone)
Emission loss (radiator) [kWh/m ² /a]	1.0	0.9
Distribution loss (heating system pipelines) [kWh/m ² /a]	5.4	4.7
Generation loss (DH substation) [kWh/m ² /a]	2.1	1.9
DHW* [kWh/m ² /a]	8.5	8.5

*Generation, circulation, and distribution.

In the Kyiv climate zone model default version, heating system distribution losses are equal to 10 % of heating energy supplied to the zones. For the Odesa climate zone, as well as the improved versions of the building, the same percentage of distribution losses as the default version will be assumed.

6.1.2 Default version energy consumption

Table 23 presents the main energy consumption components for the default version of the building for both climate zones. Primary energy is also presented, calculated with primary energy factors presented in Table 8.

Table 23. Simulation model annual energy consumption with default parameters, per total building area (12 000 m²), losses included.

		Kyiv climate zone	Odesa climate zone
Heating energy consumption [kWh/m ² /a]	final	53	47
Cooling energy consumption [kWh/m ² /a]	final	19	25
DHW final energy consumption [kWh/m ² /a]		44	44
Electricity (lights & equipment) [kWh/m ² /a]		21	21
Electricity (facility) [kWh/m ² /a]		2	2
Total energy consumption [kWh/m ² /a]	primary	199	196

The heating load is a bit higher, and the cooling load is lower in the colder region of Kyiv than in the warm coastal city of Odesa. The energy consumption components are visualised in Figure 11.

Figure 11. Energy consumption of apartment building default model.

6.2 Parametric studies

Parametric studies were conducted to each studied energy efficiency related component, to study their technical potential for energy saving. Ranges of studied parameters were kept within technically plausible ranges. Kyiv climate zone (Northern region) was used for the climate and selection basis for default (baseline) U-values of the building. For ventilation heat recovery both Kyiv and Odesa climate zones were studied. The main studied components were U-values of external wall, roof, floor and windows, and ventilation heat recovery efficiency. Additional parametric studies were made to highlight the effect of infiltration and window area. The main parametric studies are presented in Figure 12, Figure 13, Figure 14, Figure 15 and Figure 16 further below.

Figure 12. Change in apartment building heating and cooling energy consumption with external wall U-value improvement, Kyiv climate zone.

Figure 13. Change in apartment building heating and cooling energy consumption with window U-value improvement, Kyiv climate zone.

Figure 14. Change in apartment building heating and cooling energy consumption with roof U-value improvement, Kyiv climate zone.

Increasing the thickness of the roof insulation was found to have minimal effect on the heating energy of the building (Figure 14). There are several reasons to this: the top of the building is already quite well insulated, and the top area forms only 14 % of total envelope since the building is tall. In addition, the top insulation in the building is not situated in the actual roof structure of the building, but instead between the 9th floor (topmost heated floor) and the unheated technical space. Therefore, the technical floor itself insulates the building to some extent.

Figure 15. Change in apartment building heating and cooling energy consumption with floor U-value improvement, Kyiv climate zone.

Similarly, to the top insulation, increasing insulation in the floor slab of the building (below the basement) (Figure 15), has negligible effect on the building’s heat energy consumption.

Figure 16. Change in apartment building heating and cooling energy consumption with ventilation heat recovery efficiency improvement, Kyiv climate zone.

In Kyiv ventilation heat recovery resulted in some increase of cooling load (Figure 16). This is because VHR increases the length of the cooling season, as free cooling (cooling the apartment with cool ambient air) potential is reduced. Figure 17 shows the hourly air temperature within one apartment without VHR (left) and with VHR (right).

Figure 17. Room temperature of one zone without ventilation heat recovery (left) and with 80 % efficiency ventilation heat recovery (right).

It is seen that implementing ventilation heat recovery increases the length of the cooling season (in Figure 17 the period during which room temperature is at 26 °C, which is the cooling setpoint). This effect can be avoided by summer by-pass of the heat exchanger, which was not simulated in this study.

Figure 18. Change in apartment building heating and cooling energy consumption with ventilation heat recovery efficiency improvement, Odesa climate zone.

In Odesa region similar the increase in cooling load is smaller than in Kyiv (Figure 16) is not experienced. This is since free cooling potential in Odesa climate is much smaller – temperature barely drops below 15 °C during summertime.

Table 24 summarizes the parametric studies of all components.

Table 24. Summary of parametric studies on energy efficiency.

Studied component	Studied range	Max. change in heating energy	Max. change in cooling energy
External wall U-value	0.25 – 0.075 W/m ² K	6.7 %	-5.3 %
Window U-value	1.11 – 0.56 W/m ² K	11.4 %	-13.0 %
Roof U-value	0.17 – 0.05 W/m ² K	0.9 %	0 %
Floor U-value	0.2 – 0.075 W/m ² K	0.4 %	0.1 %

Ventilation HR efficiency (Kyiv)	0 – 90 %	64.0 %	-13.2 %
Ventilation HR efficiency (Odesa)	0 – 80 %	67.0 %	-2.9 %

Of the studied components, ventilation heat recovery has by far the largest energy saving potential in the studied building. This is because currently no means of recovering ventilation air energy have been employed, whereas for U-values relatively stringent requirements are already in place. Window U-value has the second highest potential for energy saving, and external wall U-value the third. Saving potential of floor and roof improvements is negligible.

Most improvements introduced increase in cooling energy consumption, in addition to decreasing heating energy, since if the building is better insulated, there is more heat trapped and hence, during summers, it requires more cooling. Ventilation heat recovery, on the other hand, reduces free cooling by supply air, as explained before. However, the absolute heating consumption in Ukraine is higher than cooling (Figure 11), and therefore the effect of all improvements in the parametric study to overall energy consumption is still net positive.

6.2.1 Increasing U-value with insulation thickness

It should be noted that for insulation thickness – based U-values (external walls, roof, floor), that the energy savings scale proportionally to the U-value of the envelope, but the U-value is inversely proportional to insulation thickness. This leads to diminishing energy efficiency improvement beyond a certain point of insulation thickness, as demonstrated in Figure 19 below.

Figure 19. External wall insulation thickness as a function of U-value.

6.2.2 Effect of window area

The impact of window U-value improvements is highly dependent on window per envelope area of the building, which is not dictated by any standard or requirement. The model apartment building has a high window per envelope area (22.7 %), partly due to the presence of glazed

balconies. Therefore, additional simulations were performed with alternative window per envelope ratios Figure 20 and Figure 21.

Figure 20. Effect of window area percentage on heating energy savings by window U-value improvement.

Figure 21. Effect of window area percentage on heating energy savings by external wall U-value improvement.

Reducing window area percentage is seen to have a relatively high effect on the benefit from window U-value improvement, but negligible effect on benefit from external wall U-value improvement. With the lower window/envelope percentage, improving window U-values has similar maximum energy saving impact as the external wall U-value improvement.

6.2.3 Effect of infiltration

A parametric study was also conducted for energy impact of building airtightness. Infiltration air consists of airflows through leaking seals by Although improving airtightness was not included as a separate improvement in the cost efficiency study, airtightness influences the energy efficiency of the building, and in practice it causes a degree of uncertainty in both modelling and the performance of actual buildings. Regulations are in place to direct construction of more airtight buildings (Table 12). Figure 22 displays the effect of reducing infiltration as per the levels in Figure 22.

Figure 22. The impact of infiltration on the apartment building heating energy consumption.

6.3 Improvement combinations

Based on the parametric studies presented above, discrete improvements were chosen to be included in an analysis of combined improvements (Table 25). All possible combinations of the selected improvements were to be simulated and analysed. Therefore, a balance had to be made to keep the amount of simulation cases in control but include enough points of interest. The aim was to also keep the improvements in a practically implementable range.

The studied improvements, yielding a total of 144 combinations, are presented in the table below. For Kyiv and Odesa cases the default cases are different (due to different regulations), but the improvement levels are the same.

Table 25. Studied apartment building discrete energy efficiency improvements, Kyiv, and Odesa

Energy efficiency					
	External wall	Roof	Floor	Windows	VHR
	U -value [W/m ² K]	Efficiency [%]			
Default (Odesa)	0.286	0.18	0.25	1.43	0
Default (Kyiv)	0.25	0.17	0.2	1.11	0
Improvement level 1	0.22	0.1	0.12	1	40
Improvement level 2	0.18	-	-	0.8	80
Improvement level 3	-	-	-	0.6	-

Initial cost estimates for the individual improvements were acquired by taking corresponding cost data from Finnish statistics and converting it to Eastern European cost level by Eurostat index [56] (Table 26 and Table 27).

Table 26. Unit costs for apartment building energy efficiency improvements, Kyiv, and Odesa.

Energy efficiency					
	External wall	Roof	Floor	Windows	VHR
	Cost [€/ext. wall m ²]	Cost [€/ roof m ²]	Cost [€/ floor m ²]	Cost [€/ window m ²]	Cost [€/unit*]
Default (Odesa)	97	54	45	222	20600
Default (Kyiv)	100	55	48	245	20600
Improvement level 1	103	60	52	253	25200
Improvement level 2	111	-	-	274	30900
Improvement level 3	-	-	-	298	-

*Unit capacity 750 l/s

Table 27. Absolute costs for energy efficiency improvements of the apartment building, Kyiv, and Odesa.

Energy efficiency					
	External wall	Roof	Floor	Windows	VHR*
	Cost [k€]	Cost [k€]	Cost [k€]	Cost [k€]	Cost [k€]
Default (Odesa)	394	61	51	414	185
Default (Kyiv)	407	62	54	457	185
Improvement level 1	418	68	59	472	227
Improvement level 2	451	-	-	511	278
Improvement level 3	-	-	-	556	-

*Assuming total of 9 ventilation units in the building

Table 28 shows the absolute costs of Table 27 divided by the total number of apartments (160).

Table 28. Per-apartment absolute costs for energy efficiency improvements of the apartment building, Kyiv, and Odesa.

Energy efficiency					
	External wall	Roof	Floor	Windows	VHR*
	Cost [€]	Cost [€]	Cost [€]	Cost [€]	Cost [€]
Default (Odesa)	2460	380	320	2590	1160
Default (Kyiv)	2540	390	340	2860	1160

Improvement level 1	2610	420	370	2950	1420
Improvement level 2	2820	-	-	3200	1740
Improvement level 3	-	-	-	3470	-

*Assuming total of 9 ventilation units in the building

6.4 Economical potential assessment

6.4.1 Methodology and input parameters

The economical impact analysis is done by NPV (net present value) method, where future payments (maintenance costs, component replacements and residuals) are discounted to the current day cost level, using a discount factor. By this method, the profitability of each studied improvement combination is shown by comparing its lifetime to that of the default case. Table 29 includes the general parameters used in the NPV study of the apartment building.

Table 29. Economical parameters for the NPV calculations of the apartment building improvements.

Discount rate, i	8 % ²⁵
Energy price escalation, f_e	2 %
Analysis period, n	50 years

Table 30 and Table 31 include component-level parameters used in the NPV study of the apartment building.

Table 30. Building component lifetimes.

Component	Lifetime [a]
Window	30
ExtWall	50
Floor	50
Roof	50
Ventilation system	20
PV	25

Table 31. Building component maintenance costs.

Component	Annual maintenance cost [% of investment]
Window	0.5
ExtWall	0

²⁵ <https://bank.gov.ua/en/markets/interest-rates?startdate=2019-01-01&enddate=2022-10-13>

Floor	0
Roof	0
Ventilation system	4
PV	1

Energy price change includes the overall inflation (assumed same as the interest rate) and energy price escalation. The discount factor for annual energy cost is then defined as [57]

$$a''n = \frac{1-(1+r_e)^{-n}}{r_e}, \tag{1}$$

where r_e is the real interest rate for energy, defined as

$$r_e = \frac{i-f_e}{1+f_e}, \tag{2}$$

where f_e is energy escalation.

Discount factor for annual maintenance cost:

$$d = \frac{1}{i} \left(1 - \frac{1}{(1+i)^n} \right) \tag{3}$$

Component replacement costs are occurring during single year, not recurring annually. The discount factor for replacement costs is defined as:

$$r = \frac{1}{(1+r)^{n_r}}, \tag{4}$$

where n_r is the year at which the replacement takes place, a.

6.4.2 Results, Kyiv

NPV was calculated to each possible combination of the improvements presented in Table 25. Figure 23 displays heating energy consumption and life cycle cost for each case.

Figure 23. Total cost versus space heating consumption for apartment building improvement combinations, Kyiv.

From the figure we can see that with the combination of the best levels of all the improvements, it is possible to reach almost as low as 10 kWh/m² of heating energy. Three distinct groups are seen in the figure, signifying the efficiency of ventilation heat recovery (since it has a dominating effect on heating energy consumption). Within these groups, the points are seen to be divided into smaller subgroups depending on window improvement level, which has the second highest impact after VHR.

The three groups are not identical in shape, for example it is seen that the vertical deviation in the uppermost group is higher than in the lowermost group – this is due to the VHR improvement decreasing the periods of time during which heating is needed. As VHR reduces the cooling effect of the supply air, it is more frequent also during winter that the internal heat gains and solar heat gains are enough to heat the building above the heating setpoint of 20 °C (as seen before in Figure 17). During these times the heating system does not need to operate, and therefore the benefit from further reducing heat loss by other improvements is lesser.

Figure 24 displays cooling energy consumption and life cycle cost for each case.

Figure 24. Total cost versus space cooling consumption for apartment building improvement combinations, Kyiv.

In Figure 24, all improvement combinations are seen to increase the cooling consumption, but the absolute change is less than that of heating energy. VHR is seen to increase the increase of cooling energy consumption caused by the other improvements. This effect is the opposite of what was seen with heating energy in Figure 23; since VHR increases building summertime temperature (Figure 17), and therefore increases the length of the cooling season, it amplifies the cooling increase by other improvements as well.

Figure 25 shows improvement effect to total purchased energy, including cooling (as electricity, since the cooling energy is produced by an air conditioning machine with COP of 3), heating, DHW, lighting, equipment, and HVAC electricity.

Figure 25. Total cost versus purchased energy for apartment building improvement combinations, Kyiv.

The points are in a similar shape as in Figure 23, since the main difference in purchased energy between the cases comes from heating energy. When zooming in into the group with no ventilation heat recovery, the effect of other improvements can be visualized (Figure 26):

Figure 26. Total cost versus purchased energy for apartment building improvements excluding ventilation heat recovery, Kyiv.

In the close-up the relative cost-effectiveness of different improvements can be seen – for example external wall upgrade 1 and window upgrade 1 have around the same total cost, but the latter enables almost around double the energy saving. The floor upgrade is seen cost-effectiveness-wise to be the weakest improvement, with no net decrease in energy but increased costs compared to default. Figure 27 shows a similar close-up into the group with 80 % VHR efficiency.

Figure 27. Total cost versus purchased energy for apartment building improvements with 80 % efficiency of ventilation heat recovery, Kyiv.

Compared to the group with no VHR (Figure 26), the range of vertical axis is lower and the range of horizontal axis is higher, as the improvements bring less overall savings, and (due to this) they increase the life cycle cost more.

Based on all the simulated improvement combinations, the components of purchased energy of selected scenarios (least energy, least energy excluding ventilation heat recovery, and least cost) are shown in Figure 28 and Table 32.

Figure 28. Components of purchased energy for selected scenarios of apartment building improvements, Kyiv.

Table 32. Components of purchased energy for selected scenarios of apartment building improvements, Kyiv.

	Heating [kWh/m ²]	Cooling [kWh/m ²]	DHW [kWh/m ²]	Electricity (lights & equipment) [kWh/m ²]	Electricity (facility) [kWh/m ²]	Total purchased Energy [kWh/m ²]	Purchased energy change
Default	53.4	6.3	43.5	20.8	2.2	126.2	-
Least energy no VHR	44.1	7.1	43.5	20.8	2.2	117.7	-7 %
Least energy	10.1	8.6	43.5	20.8	11.9	94.9	-25 %
Least lifetime cost	16.8	7.3	43.5	20.8	11.9	100.3	-21 %

Table 33 includes the improvement parameters and life cycle cost for the cases in Table 32.

Table 33. Parameters and cost for selected scenarios of apartment building improvements, Kyiv.

Case Number	Case	U-value [W/m ² K]				VHR efficiency [%]	Lifetime cost [k€]	Lifetime cost change
		Window	External wall	Floor	Roof			
1	Default	1.11	0.25	0.2	0.17	0	854	-
2	Least energy without VHR	0.6	0.18	0.12	0.1	0	935	+9 %
3	Least energy	0.6	0.18	0.12	0.1	80	899	+5 %
4	Least cost	1.11	0.25	0.2	0.17	80	780	-9 %

6.4.3 Results, Odesa

Figure 29 shows the heating energy and total lifetime cost for each combination in Odesa climate zone.

Figure 29. Total cost versus space heating consumption for apartment building improvement combinations, Odesa.

The heating load is lower, but overall, the improvement combinations behave in similar way as in Kyiv climate zone. Figure 30 shows the cooling energy and total lifecycle cost for each combination

Figure 30. Total cost versus space cooling consumption for apartment building improvement combinations, Odesa.

For Odesa, all improvements increase the cooling consumption, as is the case for Kyiv. Ventilation heat recovery increases cooling consumption less than in Kyiv climate zone (Figure 25), this was also suggested by the technical parametric studies (Figure 16 and Figure 18). Figure 31 shows improvement combinations' total lifetime cost and total purchased energy.

Figure 31. Total cost versus purchased energy for apartment building improvement combinations, Odesa.

Figure 32 is a close-up to the point group with no ventilation heat recovery, showing the effect of individual improvements.

Figure 32. Total cost versus purchased energy for apartment building improvements excluding ventilation heat recovery, Odesa.

It is seen that the cost-effectiveness for Odesa is largely like situation in Kyiv (Figure 26), in that no individual improvements are profitable. Figure 33 shows a close-up into the group with 80 % VHR efficiency.

Figure 33. Total cost versus purchased energy for apartment building improvements with 80 % efficiency of ventilation heat recovery, Odesa.

Based on all the simulated improvement combinations, least energy, least energy excluding ventilation heat recovery, and least cost scenarios are shown in Figure 34.

Figure 34. Components of purchased energy for selected scenarios of apartment building improvements, Odesa.

The most differences are seen in the heating load and added auxiliary (facility) electricity for the least energy and least lifecycle cost cases. Table 34 shows the same in numerical format.

Table 34. Components of purchased energy for selected scenarios of apartment building improvements, Odesa.

	Heating [kWh/m ²]	Cooling [kWh/m ²]	DHW [kWh/m ²]	Electricity (lights & equipment) [kWh/m ²]	Electricity (facility) [kWh/m ²]	Total purchased energy [kWh/m ²]	Purchased energy change
Default	47.0	8.3	43.5	20.8	2.2	121.8	-
Least energy no VHR	33.6	9.5	43.5	20.8	2.2	109.6	-10 %
Least energy	4.4	10.4	43.5	20.8	11.9	91.0	-25 %
Least lifetime cost	13.1	8.7	43.5	20.8	11.9	98.0	-20 %

Table 35 shows the parameters and the lifecycle cost for the cases in Table 34.

Table 35. Parameters and cost for selected scenarios of apartment building improvements, Odesa.

Case Number	Case	U-value [W/m ² K]				VHR efficiency [%]	Life cycle cost [k€]	Life cycle cost change
		Window	External wall	Floor	Roof			
1	Default (Odesa)	1.43	0.29	0.25	0.18	0	812	-
2	Least energy without VHR	0.6	0.18	0.12	0.1	0	933	+15 %
3	Least energy	0.6	0.18	0.12	0.1	80	932	+15 %
4	Least cost	1.43	0.29	0.25	0.18	80	759	-7 %

6.5 Sensitivity studies

The effect of the uncertainty of selected economical parameters' (energy price, investment prices and discount rate) to the results is studied in this chapter. More specifically, the life cycle cost of the four presented scenarios (e.g., Table 35) as a function of these economical parameters is presented Table 35. Parameters and cost for selected scenarios of apartment building improvements, Odesa.

6.5.1 Energy price

The energy prices used in this report (chapter 5.10) are from spring 2022. Ukraine's economical situation during 2022 is unstable due to Russian invasion, and the country's energy system has suffered damage in bombings, therefore the energy prices are subject to high uncertainty. Table 36 shows the apartment building energy prices for 50 % and 100 % price level increases.

Table 36. Apartment building energy prices for sensitivity study.

			Original	50 % increase	100 % increase
Kyiv	Heating	energy	0.05	0.075	0.1
	Electrical	energy	0.06	0.09	0.12
Odesa	Heating	energy	0.06	0.09	0.12
	Electrical	energy	0.06	0.09	0.12

6.5.1.1.1 Kyiv

Figure 35 shows the life cycle cost of individual improvements for original energy price level, as well as 50 % and 100 % increased level.

Figure 35. Apartment building life cycle cost with individual improvements, original, +50 % and +100 % energy prices, Kyiv

Figure 36 presents the life cycle cost as a function of energy price increase for scenarios 1-4 of the apartment building in Kyiv region (as seen in Table 33). It is seen that as energy price increases, the life cycle cost of the default version of the building increases more than of the improved versions since the default version consumes the highest amount of energy overall. With 50 % energy price increase, the least energy version has lower life cycle cost than default, and with 100 % energy price increase the least energy without VHR version has life cycle cost equal to the default.

Figure 36. Sensitivity of apartment building improvement scenarios to change in energy prices, Kyiv.

6.5.1.1.2 Odesa

Figure 37 shows the life cycle cost of individual improvements for original energy price level, as well as 50 % and 100 % increased level.

Figure 37. Apartment building life cycle cost with individual improvements, original, +50 % and +100 % energy prices, Odesa.

Figure 38 presents the life cycle cost as a function of energy price increase for scenarios 1-4 of the apartment building in Odesa region (as seen in Table 35). The effect of energy price increase is seen as similar to the Kyiv region, with higher energy cost noticeably increasing the profitability of the improved versions compared to the default version.

Figure 38. Sensitivity of apartment building improvement scenarios to change in energy prices, Odesa.

6.5.2 Investment price

Energy efficiency improvement and investment prices were identified as another major point of uncertainty, and therefore they were included in the sensitivity study. Table 37 includes the original investment prices as well as 25 % and 50 % increased per-apartment investment prices for the apartment building.

Table 37. Apartment building investment prices for sensitivity study, with original prices per apartment, 25 % increased prices and 50 % increased prices.

Energy efficiency					
	External wall	Roof	Floor	Windows	VHR
	Cost [€], Original / +25% / +50%				
Default (Odesa)	2460/3080/3690	380/480/570	320/400/480	2590/3230/3880	1160/1450/1740
Default (Kyiv)	2540/3180/3820	390/480/580	340/420/510	2860/3570/4280	1160/1450/1740
Improvement level 1	2610/3270/3920	420/530/640	370/460/550	2950/3690/4420	1420/1770/2130
Improvement level 2	2820/3520/4220	-	-	3190/3990/4790	1740/2170/2610
Improvement level 3	-	-	-	3470/4340/5210	-

6.5.2.1.1 Kyiv

Figure 39 shows the life cycle cost of individual improvements for original investment price level, as well as 25 % and 50 % increased level.

Figure 39. Apartment building life cycle cost with individual improvements, original, +25 % and +50 % investment prices, Kyiv.

Figure 40 presents the life cycle cost as a function of investment price increase for scenarios 1-4 of the apartment building in Kyiv region (as seen in Table 33). In the figure, it is seen that the life cycle cost of the most investment-heavy scenario (least energy) increases the most. The life cycle cost of the default scenario does not change since the default level of energy efficiency components is set to zero in the calculation. With 25 % increase in investment prices, the least cost scenario remains profitable, but with 50 % increase its life cycle cost is slightly above the default scenario.

Figure 40. Sensitivity of apartment building improvement scenarios to change in investment prices, Kyiv.

6.5.2.1.2 Odesa

Figure 41 shows the life cycle cost of individual improvements for original investment price level, as well as 25 % and 50 % increased level.

Figure 41. Apartment building life cycle cost with individual improvements, original, +25 % and +50 % investment prices, Odesa.

Figure 42 presents the life cycle cost as a function of investment price increase for scenarios 1-4 of the apartment building in Kyiv region (as seen in Table 35). Similarly, to the case in Kyiv climate zone (Figure 40), the least cost scenario remains profitable with 25 % increase in investment price, but not with 50 % increase Figure 42. Figure 40. Sensitivity of apartment building improvement scenarios to change in investment prices, Kyiv.

Figure 42. Sensitivity of apartment building improvement scenarios to change in investment prices, Odesa.

6.5.3 Discount rate

Discount rate affects the present-day value of future payments, so that with higher discount rate the importance of future savings is lesser. In this chapter the effect of increasing the discount rate from 8 % to 25 % is displayed.

6.5.3.1 Kyiv

Figure 43 presents the life cycle cost as a function of discount rate for scenarios 1-4 of the apartment building in Kyiv region (as seen in Table 33). Higher discount rate favours the scenarios

with a lower investment cost, and it is seen that with discount rate of 25 %, the least cost scenario is no longer profitable, similar to what was seen in Figure 40 with increasing investment cost.

Figure 43. Sensitivity of apartment building improvement scenarios to change in discount rate, Kyiv.

6.5.3.2 Odesa

Figure 44 presents the life cycle cost as a function of discount rate for scenarios 1-4 of the apartment building in Kyiv region (as seen in Table 35). The effect of discount rate is like that in Kyiv climate zone, in that with higher discount rate least cost scenario is no longer profitable.

Figure 44. Sensitivity of apartment building improvement scenarios to change in discount rate, Odesa.

6.6 PV integration

To realise an increased share of energy produced from renewables, we utilise the potential of photovoltaic energy that could be attained from rooftop of the apartment building. By utilizing PVGIS, a tool that delivers information about solar radiation and photovoltaic system performance [58], we optimize the slope and azimuth for Kyiv and Odesa (Table 38). Despite having a roof area of only ~1100m², there is still a huge potential that could be tapped into. With lights and equipment being operated throughout the day, unlike schools (daily schedule is between 7 and 17), an effective PV matching would go a large way in reducing the imported electricity. The optimized setup of the PV panels on the roof translate to a calculated panel power of 92 kWp. Factoring in the area required for operation and maintenance and other equipment beside the panels, the generated electricity was found to be about 100 MWh/and 114 MWh/for Kyiv and Odesa respectively.

Table 38. PV parameters for the apartment building, Kyiv, and Odesa.

	Kyiv	Odesa
Panel slope, °	37	36
Panel azimuth, °	-2	1
System loss, %	14	14
Required area, m ² /kWp*	12	12
Available roof area, m ²	1100	1100
Panel power, kWp	92	92
Generated annual electricity, MWh	100	114

*Area practically required for south facing panels, considering walking paths and other equipment on the roof.

6.6.1 Kyiv region

The monthly in-plane irradiation for a fixed angle PV system for Kyiv is displayed Figure 45. The monthly irradiation profile does not reflect how it behaves on an hourly level. With the operating hours being 120 hours, a week, the inclusion of a battery or a storage device would improve the level of matching, whereas the capacity to sell the excess PV back to the grid would result in increased economic benefits.

Figure 45: Monthly in-plane irradiation for fixed angle in Kyiv

The PV-load matching was done for four different cases – the default case (Case I), improvements that led to least energy expended (Case II), improvements that led to least energy expended without the implementation of a ventilation heat recovery unit (Case III) and improvements that cost the least (Case IV). The plots for the monthly load-matching and the daily load-matching for the first week of January and the first week of June is depicted in [Annex](#).

It could be seen that for cases I and III, the absence of a ventilation heat recovery unit is reflected in lesser electric loads. The consumption, generation and the matching factor are tabulated in Table 39. It should be noted that a maximum of 24% of its electrical consumption is matched solely by PV energy.

Table 39. PV matching for default, least energy and least cost scenarios, Kyiv.

Case	Gross electricity consumption [kWh/m ²]	PV generation [kWh/m ²]	Own use PV [kWh/m ²]	Own electricity fraction*	Own electricity matching**	Net cost without PV [k€]	Net cost with PV [k€]
Default	29.3	8.3	6.9	24 %	83 %	854	883
Least energy	40.5	8.3	7.9	20 %	95 %	899	915
Least energy without VHR	30.1	8.3	7.0	23 %	84 %	935	963
Least lifetime cost	39.2	8.3	7.8	20 %	94 %	780	798

*Own use PV / Gross electricity consumption

**Own use PV / PV generation

6.6.2 Odesa region

The monthly energy output from an optimized fix-angle PV system for Odesa is displayed in Figure 46. It is observed that Odesa, located in southern Ukraine, has a higher potential for PV as compared to Kyiv. At the same time, the warm climate necessitates a relatively increased cooling load.

Figure 46: Monthly in-plane irradiation for fixed angle in Odesa

The PV-load matching was done for four different cases – the default case (Case I), improvements that led to least energy expended (Case II), improvements that led to least energy expended without the implementation of a ventilation heat recovery unit (Case III) and improvements that cost the least (Case IV). The plots for the monthly load-matching and the daily load-matching for the first week of January and the first week of June are plotted in the [Annex](#).

It could also be seen that for cases I and III, the absence of a ventilation heat recovery unit is reflected in lesser electric loads. The consumption, generation and the matching factor are tabulated in Table 40. It should be noted that a maximum of 25% of its electrical consumption is matched solely by PV energy.

Table 40. PV matching for default, least energy and least cost scenarios, Odesa.

Case	Gross electricity consumption [kWh/m ²]	PV generation [kWh/m ²]	Own use PV [kWh/m ²]	Own electricity fraction*	Own electricity matching**	Net cost without PV [k€]	Net cost with PV [k€]
Default	31.2	9.5	7.8	25 %	82 %	813	830
Least energy	42.3	9.5	8.9	21 %	94 %	932	936
Least energy without VHR	32.5	9.5	7.9	24 %	83 %	933	949
Least lifetime cost	41.2	9.5	8.8	21 %	93 %	759	765

*Own use PV / Gross electricity consumption

**Own use PV / PV generation

7. School building analysis

7.1 Selection of reference school model

With the objective of studying energy efficiency improvements in a school building, we develop a reference model of a Ukrainian school in IDA-ICE. In order to select this representative model, eight schools were considered.

Figure 47: An illustration of the Synergia Irpin school selected as the representative school for modelling.

A majority of them had some kind of limitation to be used for our modelling application – ranging from a typical geometry and lack of available design documents to reconstruction of only a part of the structure and not the whole school. After discussions and deliberations, Synergia Irpin school was selected for modelling (*Figure 47*). This school was representative of an ideal school in Ukraine, with a Lyceum united with primary school and gymnasium. The 3-floor school building was modelled based on the drawings procured. Spaces within the building are divided into zones, as per EN ISO 13790. The school has 12 entrances, and the total heated area is 13360 m². The IDA-ICE model is shown in *Figure 48* and *Figure 49*.

Figure 48: School building model in IDA-ICE

Figure 49: Floor plan of the school's ground floor in IDA-ICE

7.1.1 Input parameters

The table below (*Table 41*) is a summary of model input parameters relevant to the energy simulation. Although the reference building was built according to the earlier regulations, we make use of the upcoming regulations that came into force in September 2022.

Table 41. School building model parameters

Geometry	Windows	Ventilation	Heating system	Cooling system	Internal gains
Volume 62240 m ³	Window area 1875 m ²	Natural ventilation with no heat recovery (simulated as mechanical exhaust with zero fan power)	District heating	Cooling based on apartment-level AC	Heat from occupants 7W/m ²
External wall area 4085 m ²	Portion of envelope 12 %	Average flow rate 1.84 L/s/m ²	Setpoint 20 °C (with non-occupied period setback of 17°C)	Setpoint 24°C (with non-occupied period setback of 27°C)	Heat from lighting 7 W/m ²
Roof area 4760 m ²		Infiltration n ₅₀ = 2.0 1/h, n = 0.1 1/h	Generation efficiency 96 %	EER = 3	Heat from equipment 6 W/m ²
Ground area 4785 m ²			Radiator efficiency 98 %	Losses incorporated into the EER	Occupation period 50 hours/week
Heated floor area 13365 m ²			Distribution efficiency based on building geometry		

In the default case, there is natural ventilation, which is modelled as mechanical exhaust with zero fan power for simplicity. The ventilation system is always on. The flowrates are different for different zones, i.e., they differ between the classrooms, the sports halls, the gymnasiums (based on Table 17) and the average flowrate is around 1.84 L/s/m².

The setpoints and the associated non-occupied period setback for heating and cooling and the operating hours of the school were extracted from DSTU B A.2.2-12:2015 'Energy efficiency of buildings - Method of calculating energy consumption for heating, cooling, ventilation, lighting, and hot water supply' (Table 15). The weekends are considered as holidays, in addition to the 53 holidays spread over the year, as mentioned in Table 14. This includes the summer holidays during the months of July and August.

Table 42 lists the structures for the default version of the building. The structures are based on the information available in the received drawings. In the default case, the building has natural ventilation and does not have any ventilation heat recovery unit.

Table 42. Default building structures, and U-values for external constructions.

Structure	Layers	U-value Kyiv [W/m ² K]	U-value Odesa [W/m ² K]
External walls	Solid Clay brick	0.25	0.29
	Mineral wool		
	Sand and cement façade plaster		

Roof	Reinforced concrete	0.143	0.17
	Thermal insulation		
	Cement and sand reinforced mortar		
External floor	Ceramic granite tile	0.137	0.137
	Cement and sand mortar		
	Polystyrene Foam slab		
	Concrete		
	Sand filling		
	Soil compacted with crushed stone		
Windows	2-chamber double-glazed (4i-10-4M1-10-4i)	1.11	1.43
Internal floors	Floor coating	2.39	2.39
	L/W concrete		
	Concrete		

Thermal bridges of structures are included in the minimum U-values presented by regulations, and therefore they are not separately included. In the present study, it is assumed that for the improved insulation U-values thermal bridges are similar to the default case.

The table below (Table 43) includes the losses figures used in the school building model and based on the typical case calculations in Ukraine.

Table 43. Non-recoverable heating system & DHW losses of apartment building model, with default parameters.

Loss type	Value (Kyiv climate zone)	Value (Odesa climate zone)
Emission loss (radiator) [kWh/m ² /a]	1.9	1.9
Distribution loss (heating system pipelines) [kWh/m ² /a]	9.2	9.2
Generation loss (DH substation) [kWh/m ² /a]	2.5	2.5
DHW* [kWh/m ² /a]	8.4	8.4

*Generation, circulation, and distribution.

In the Kyiv climate zone model default version, distribution losses are equal to 9% of heating energy supplied to the zones. For the Odesa climate zone, as well as the improved versions of the building, the same percentage of distribution losses as the default (baseline) version will be assumed.

7.1.2 Default version energy consumption

The table below (*Table 44*) presents the main energy consumption figures for the baseline version of the building and Figure 50 visualises the same in terms of a bar graph.

Table 44. Simulation model annual energy consumption with default parameters, for Kyiv climate zone, losses included.

Output	Kyiv	Odesa
Heating final energy consumption [kWh/m ² /a]	128	110
Cooling final energy consumption [kWh/m ² /a]	23	33
DHW final energy consumption [kWh/m ² /a]	19	19
Electricity (lights and equipment) [kWh/m ² /a]	27	27
Electricity (facility) [kWh/m ² /a]	2	2
Total primary energy consumption [kWh/m²/a, kWh/m³/a]	293,61	268,58

Figure 50: Energy consumption of a school building default model in the two climate zones

7.2 Parametric studies

Parametric studies were conducted to study the technical potential of each energy efficiency related component. Ranges of studied parameters were kept within technically plausible ranges. Kyiv climate zone (Northern region) was used for the climate and selection basis for default (baseline) U-values of the building. The main studied components were U-values of external wall, roof, floor and windows, and ventilation heat recovery efficiency. More detail is presented in Figure 51, Figure 52, Figure 53, Figure 54, and Figure 55 further below.

Figure 51: Change in heating and cooling energy consumption with external wall U-value improvement, Kyiv climate zone

Figure 52: Change in heating and cooling energy consumption with window U-value improvement, Kyiv climate zone

As it can be observed from Figure 51, Figure 52, improving the U-values of windows and external wall by increasing the insulation thickness has been found to have an impact on the heating and cooling consumption. The window improvements are found to bring about a maximum of 4% reduction in heating consumption whereas the external wall improvements are found to have reduced the heating consumption by a maximum of 3% for the studied U-values. This could be attributed to the large surface area of the external walls and the high share of windows as a portion of the envelope.

Figure 53: Change in heating and cooling energy consumption with roof U-value improvement, Kyiv climate zone

Figure 54: Change in heating and cooling energy consumption with floor slab U-value improvement, Kyiv climate zone

Further, increasing the insulation thickness of the roof and the floor was found to have minimal effect on the energy consumption of the building (Figure 54). This could be attributed to the fact that the above-mentioned two components are already well-insulated and were built better than the previously established regulation levels.

Figure 55: Change in heating and cooling energy consumption with ventilation heat recovery efficiency improvement, (left) Kyiv climate zone and (right) Odesa climate zone

Amongst the studied components, the implementation of a ventilation heat recovery and improving its efficiency has by far the largest energy saving potential in the studied building. Presently, buildings in Ukraine have no means of recovering ventilation air energy have been employed, whereas for U-values relatively stringent requirements are already in place. Similar to the apartment building (Figure 16, Figure 18), heating energy reduction in Odesa is a bit higher in Odesa than Kyiv, and cooling energy increase is smaller owing to free cooling.

It should also be noted that even though improvements in U-values for roof, external walls and floor resulted in a reduced heating consumption, further improvements in U-value would not be feasible from a practical point of view owing to the large thickness of the insulation. Table 45 summarizes the main parametric studies on energy efficiency:

Table 45. Summary of parametric studies on energy efficiency

Component	Studied range	Maximum change in heating energy	Maximum change in cooling energy
External wall U-value [W/m ² K]	0.25 – 0.075	3.1%	-1.5%
Window U-value [W/m ² K]	1.11 – 0.56	4.3%	-4.7%
Roof U-value [W/m ² K]	0.14 – 0.06	1.8%	-1.5%
Floor U-value [W/m ² K]	0.2 – 0.08	0.2%	-0.7%
Ventilation efficiency HR	0% – 90%	90%	-44%

As it can be observed from the above table, the improvements in U-values (or the implementation of a VHR unit) are also seen to increase the cooling consumption. For VHR, this is due to reduced free cooling by supply air in summer, although it is possible to circumvent this effect by bypassing the heat exchanger. U-value improvements also increase the cooling consumption, since if the building is better insulated, there is more heat trapped and hence, during summers, it requires more cooling

7.3 Improvement combinations

Based on the parametric studies presented above, discrete improvements were chosen to be included in an analysis of combined improvements (Table 46). All possible combinations of the selected improvements were to be simulated and analysed. Therefore, a balance had to be made to keep the amount of simulation cases in control but include enough points of interest. The aim was to also keep the improvements in a practically implementable range.

The studied improvements, yielding a total of 144 combinations, are presented in the table below. For Kyiv and Odesa climate zones, the default cases are distinct (due to differing regulations), but the improvement levels are the same.

Table 46. Studied school building discrete energy efficiency improvements, Kyiv, and Odesa

Energy efficiency					
	External wall	Roof	Floor	Windows	VHR
	U-value [W/m ² K]	Efficiency [%]			

Default (Odesa)	0.286	0.17	0.25	1.43	0
Default (Kyiv)	0.25	0.143	0.2	1.11	0
Improvement level 1	0.22	0.1	0.12	1	40
Improvement level 2	0.18	-	-	0.8	80
Improvement level 3	-	-	-	0.6	-

Initial cost estimates for the individual improvements were acquired by taking corresponding cost data from Finnish statistics and converting it to Eastern European cost level by Eurostat index [56] Table 47 and Table 48. As stated earlier, for the NPV calculations, the default level of the studied parameters was set to 0 (Kyiv or Odesa), and only the relative increments in cost were considered.

Table 47. Unit costs for school building energy efficiency improvements, Kyiv, and Odesa.

Energy efficiency					
	External wall	Roof	Floor	Windows	VHR*
	Cost [€/ext. wall m ²]	Cost [€/ roof m ²]	Cost [€/ floor m ²]	Cost [€/ window m ²]	Cost [€]
Default (Odesa)	97	54	45	222	20600
Default (Kyiv)	100	56	48	245	20600
Improvement level 1	103	60	52	253	25200
Improvement level 2	111	-	-	274	30900
Improvement level 3	-	-	-	298	-

*Unit capacity 750 l/s

The cost of the ventilation heat recovery unit was found to be very high because schools in Ukraine have high ventilation flow rates and this necessitates a total of 33 units, thereby increasing the costs.

Table 48: Absolute costs for energy efficiency improvements of the school building, Kyiv, and Odesa.

Energy efficiency improvement parameters					
	External wall	Roof	Floor	Windows	VHR*
	Cost [k€]	Cost [k€]	Cost [k€]	Cost [k€]	Cost [k€]
Default (Odesa)	396	257	215	416	680
Default (Kyiv)	407	267	230	459	680
Improvement level 1	421	286	249	474	832

Improvement level 2	454	-	-	513	1020
Improvement level 3	-	-	-	558	-

*Assuming total of 33 ventilation units in the building

7.4 Economical potential assessment

7.4.1 Methodology and input parameters

The economic impact analysis is done by using NPV (net present value) method, where future payments (maintenance costs, component replacements and residuals) are discounted to the current day cost level, using a discount factor. Table 49 includes the general parameters used in the NPV study of the school building. For the school building, the economical parameters are the same as for the apartment building, except for the analysis period, which is 30 years instead of 50 years. The building component lifetimes and their maintenance costs are the same as for the apartment building and have been tabulated earlier in Table 30 and Table 31. The discount factors for the annual energy cost, the maintenance cost, energy price escalation, the replacement cost and the other accompanying calculations have been explained earlier and the results are now presented in the subsequent sections.

Table 49. Economical parameters for the school building.

Discount rate, i	8 % ²⁶
Energy price escalation, f_e	2 %
Analysis period, n	30 years

7.4.2 Results, Kyiv

The total cost, which is the sum of the investment cost, the replacement cost, the maintenance cost, the energy cost and factors in the residual cost as well is calculated and is plotted against the space heating consumption for the 144 cases simulated according to Table 46. We observe three distinct 'clouds/levels' of the plots with the reduced energy consumption due to implementation of ventilation heat recovery unit being the dominant factor (Figure 56). A ventilation heat recovery unit with an 80% efficiency installed results in the heating energy reduction to less than 20 kWh/m².

²⁶ <https://bank.gov.ua/en/markets/interest-rates?startdate=2019-01-01&enddate=2022-10-13>

Figure 56: Total cost versus space heating consumption for school building improvement combinations, Kyiv.

On the other hand, the ventilation heat recovery unit also increases the cooling consumption. The result of this phenomena is visualised in Figure 57. The cumulative effect of these phenomena is studied by means of a total life cycle cost versus purchased energy plot, as illustrated in Figure 58.

Figure 57: Total life cycle cost versus space cooling consumption for school building improvement combinations, Kyiv.

Figure 58: Total cost versus purchased energy for school building improvement combinations, Kyiv.

As opposed to the apartment building, the heating and electricity tariffs are relatively high for the school building in both Kyiv and Odesa. As a result, the implementation of a ventilation heat recovery unit reduces the overall cost. Amongst the two improvement levels of the heat recovery unit, 40% efficiency and 80% efficiency, since the heat reduction is greater in the latter and the electricity consumption is the same for both, a ventilation heat recovery unit with 80% efficiency was found to result in greatest cost savings. The effect of improvements of all parameters except ventilation heat recovery is further studied and is illustrated in Figure 59. The labelled points are results of individual improvements; unlabelled blue points are the result of combining different improvements.

Figure 59: Total cost versus purchased energy for school building improvements excluding ventilation heat recovery, Kyiv.

It is seen that of individual upgrades, improvement level 1 of roof and window result in profitable scenarios as their total lifetime cost is lower than that of the default case. Figure 60 shows a close-up into the group with 80 % VHR efficiency.

Figure 60. Total cost versus purchased energy for school building improvements with 80 % efficiency of ventilation heat recovery Kyiv.

Combined with 80 % efficiency VHR, none of the other improvements remain profitable. After simulating the 144 cases for varying degrees of improvements in the parameters, four specific cases were studied in detail further. They are tabulated in Table 50.

Table 50: Components for selected scenarios of school building improvements, Kyiv.

Case Number	Case	U-value [W/m ² K]				VHR efficiency [%]	Life cycle cost [k€]	Life cycle cost change
		Window	External wall	Floor	Roof			
1	Default (Kyiv)	1.11	0.25	0.2	0.143	0	3411	-
2	Least energy without VHR	0.6	0.18	0.12	0.1	0	3462	+1 %
3	Least energy	0.6	0.18	0.2	0.1	80	2888	-15 %
4	Least cost	1.11	0.25	0.2	0.143	80	2766	-19 %

Figure 61 illustrates the share of each energy carrier out of the total purchased energy for the school building in Kyiv region and Table 51 translates the same into numbers.

Figure 61: Components of purchased energy for selected scenarios of school building improvements, Kyiv.

Table 51. Components of purchased energy for selected scenarios of school building improvements, Kyiv.

	Heating [kWh/m ²]	Cooling [kWh/m ²]	DHW [kWh/m ²]	Electricity (lights & equipment) [kWh/m ²]	Electricity (facility) [kWh/m ²]	Total purchased energy [kWh/m ²]	Purchased energy change
Default	127.5	7.7	18.8	27.1	2.2	183.3	-
Least energy no VHR	119.6	8.1	18.8	27.1	2.2	175.8	-4 %

Least energy	10.8	12.2	18.8	27.1	31.2	100.1	-45 %
Least cost	15.0	10.99	18.8	27.1	31.2	103.1	-44 %

7.4.3 Results, Odesa

The total cost is calculated and is plotted against the space heating consumption for the 144 cases simulated for Odesa climate zone according to Table 46. Similar to the previous case, we observe three distinct ‘clouds/levels’ of the plots with the reduced energy consumption due to implementation of ventilation heat recovery unit. A ventilation heat recovery unit with an 80% efficiency installed results in the heating energy reduction to less than 20 kWh/m² (Figure 62). On the other hand, the ventilation heat recovery unit also increases the cooling consumption. The result of this phenomena is visualised in Figure 63.

Figure 62. Total cost versus space heating consumption for school building improvement combinations, Odesa.

Figure 63. Total cost versus space cooling consumption for school building improvement combinations, Odesa.

The cumulative effect of the above-mentioned heating and cooling related phenomena is studied further by means of a total lifetime cost versus purchased energy plot, as illustrated in Figure 64.

Figure 64. Total lifetime cost versus purchased energy for school building improvement combinations, Odesa.

As stated earlier, the heating and electricity tariffs of the school building are almost thrice that of an apartment building in Odesa. Similar to previous case, a ventilation heat recovery unit with 80% efficiency results in a reduced cost as compared with the default scenario. But, here since the electricity tariff is quite high (0.21€/kWh), the electricity used to power the unit in addition to the heating costs makes the 40% efficient ventilation heat recovery unit an unlikely candidate to

reap economic benefits. The effect of improvements of all parameters except ventilation heat recovery is studied in detail and is depicted in Figure 65.

Figure 65. Total cost versus purchased energy for school building improvements excluding ventilation heat recovery, Odesa.

The labelled points are results of individual improvements; unlabelled blue points are the result of combining different improvements. It is seen that of individual upgrades, roof upgrade and window upgrade level 1 are profitable, as their total lifetime cost is lower than that of the default case. Figure 66 shows a close-up into the group with 80 % VHR efficiency.

Figure 66. Total cost versus purchased energy for school building improvements with 80 % efficiency of ventilation heat recovery, Odesa.

Combined with 80 % efficiency VHR, none of the other improvements remain profitable.

After simulating the 144 cases for varying degrees of improvements in the parameters, four specific cases were studied in detail further. They are tabulated in Table 52.

Table 52. Parameters and cost for selected scenarios of school building improvements, Odesa.

Case Number	Case	U-value [W/m ² K]				VHR efficiency [%]	Life cycle cost [k€]	Life cycle cost change
		Window	External wall	Floor	Roof			
1	Default (Odesa)	1.43	0.29	0.25	0.17	0	3832	-
2	Least energy without VHR	0.6	0.18	0.12	0.1	0	3906	+2 %
3	Least energy	0.6	0.18	0.25	0.1	80	3748	-2 %
4	Least cost	1.43	0.29	0.25	0.17	80	3552	-7 %

Figure 67 illustrates the share of each energy carrier out of the total purchased energy for the school building in Kyiv region and Table 53 translates the same into numbers.

Figure 67. Components of purchased energy for selected scenarios of school building improvements, Odesa.

Table 53. Components of purchased energy for selected scenarios of school building improvements, Odesa.

	Heating	Cooling	DHW	Electricity (lights & equipment)	Electricity (facility)	Total purchased energy	Purchased energy change
Default/least lifetime cost	110.1	10.9	18.8	27.1	2.2	169.1	-

Least energy no VHR	99.4	11.6	18.8	27.1	2.2	159.1	-6 %
Least energy	5.1	14.8	18.8	27.1	31.2	97.0	-43 %
Least cost	10.2	13.1	18.8	27.1	31.2	100.4	-41 %

7.5 Sensitivity studies

Sensitivity studies are conducted for the school building in the similar manner as for the apartment building in chapter 6.5.

7.5.1 Energy price

Energy price is the first studied economical parameter in the sensitivity study. Table 54 shows the school building energy prices for 50 % and 100 % price level increases.

Table 54. School building energy prices for sensitivity study.

			Original	50 % increase	100 % increase
Kyiv	Heating energy [€/kWh]		0.10	0.15	0.2
	Electrical energy [€/kWh]		0.15	0.225	0.3
Odesa	Heating energy [€/kWh]		0.11	0.165	0.22
	Electrical energy [€/kWh]		0.21	0.315	0.42

7.5.1.1.1 Kyiv

Figure 68 shows the life cycle cost of individual improvements for original energy price level, as well as 50 % and 100 % increased level.

Figure 68. School building life cycle cost with individual improvements, original, +50 % and +100 % energy prices, Kyiv

Figure 69 presents the life cycle cost as a function of energy price increase for scenarios 1-4 of the school building in Kyiv region (as seen in Table 50). The scenarios including 80 % VHR (least energy and least cost) are seen to become more profitable with increasing energy price, even

beyond the obvious

though the cost of fan electricity consumed by the ventilation units is increased more than heating energy in absolute terms, due to its higher original price.

Figure 69. Sensitivity of school building improvement scenarios to change in energy prices, Kyiv.

7.5.1.1.2 Odesa

Figure 70 shows the life cycle cost of individual improvements for original energy price level, as well as 50 % and 100 % increased level.

Figure 70. School building life cycle cost with individual improvements, original, +50 % and +100 % energy prices, Odesa.

Figure 71 presents the life cycle cost as a function of energy price increase for scenarios 1-4 of the school building in Odesa region (as seen in Table 52). The cost of cases with VHR (least energy and least cost) is in the starting point closer to cases without VHR than in the case of Kyiv (Figure 69), since in Odesa the gap between heating energy price and electricity price is higher. The slopes of scenarios including VHR are also closer to the slopes of scenarios not including VHR due to the same reason, but the former scenarios are seen to still become somewhat more profitable with increasing energy prices. Thereby investments in ventilation heat recovery not only remain profitable but increase in profitability as energy prices increase.

Figure 71. Sensitivity of school building improvement scenarios to change in energy prices, Odesa.

7.5.2 Investment price

Investment price is second studied economical parameter in the sensitivity study. Table 55 includes the original investment prices as well as 25 % and 50 % increased investment prices for the school building.

Table 55. School building investment prices for sensitivity study, with original prices, 25 % increased prices and 50 % increased prices.

Energy efficiency					
	External wall	Roof	Floor	Windows	VHR
	Cost [k€], Original / +25% / +50%				
Default (Odesa)	396/495/594	257/321/386	215/269/323	416/520/624	680/850/1020
Default (Kyiv)	407/509/611	267/333/400	230/287/344	460/574/689	680/850/1020
Improvement level 1	421/526/631	286/357/428	249/311/373	474/592/711	832/1040/1247
Improvement level 2	454/567/680	-	-	513/642/770	1020/1275/1530
Improvement level 3	-	-	-	558/698/837	-

7.5.2.1.1 Kyiv

Figure 70 shows the life cycle cost of individual improvements for original investment price level, as well as 25 % and 50 % increased level.

Figure 72. School building life cycle cost with individual improvements, original, +25 % and +50 % energy prices, Kyiv.

Figure 73 presents the life cycle cost as a function of investment price increase for scenarios 1-4 of the school building in Kyiv region (as seen in Table 50). Least energy and least cost scenarios lose profitability, but their LCC remains lower than the default even with 50 % price increase.

Figure 73. Sensitivity of school building improvement scenarios to change in investment prices, Kyiv.

7.5.2.1.2 Odesa

Figure 74 shows the life cycle cost of individual improvements for original investment price level, as well as 25 % and 50 % increased level.

Figure 74. School building life cycle cost with individual improvements, original, +25 % and +50 % energy prices, Odesa.

Figure 75 presents the life cycle cost as a function of investment price increase for scenarios 1-4 of the school building in Odesa region (as seen in Table 52). In Odesa the least energy scenario quickly loses its profitability investment price increases. Least cost scenario remains profitable until 50 % increase in investment price, where its LCC is equal to that of the default scenario.

Figure 75. Sensitivity of school building improvement scenarios to change in investment prices, Odesa.

7.5.3 Discount rate

As stated earlier in Section 5.10, we do a sensitivity analysis for the interest rates (8% and 25%). This large difference in the rates is attributed to the uncertainty in circumstances owing to war.

7.5.3.1 Kyiv

Figure 76 presents the life cycle cost as a function of investment price increase for scenarios 1-4 of the school building in Kyiv region (as seen in Table 50). With 25 % discount rate all the scenarios converge to roughly the same LCC.

Figure 76. Sensitivity of school building improvement scenarios to change in discount rate, Kyiv.

7.5.3.2 Odesa

Figure 77 presents the life cycle cost as a function of investment price increase for scenarios 1-4 of the school building in Odesa region (as seen in Table 52).

As discussed in section 7.4.3, the high electricity tariff for schools in Odesa renders a ventilation heat recovery unit with 40% efficiency unfeasible from an economic point of view. For an 8% interest rate, the implementation of a ventilation heat recovery unit with 80% efficiency led to energy and cost savings. Now, for the war-time interest rate of 25%, implementation of a ventilation heat recovery unit did not result in cost savings, as it can be observed from Figure 77. Sensitivity of school building improvement scenarios to change in discount rate, Kyiv.

Figure 77. Sensitivity of school building improvement scenarios to change in discount rate, Kyiv.

7.6 PV integration

The clause 6 of the draft by-law [59] advocates for an increased of share of energy produced from renewable sources for self-consumption. In order to realise that we try to maximise the potential of PV energy that could be attained from rooftop of the school building.

By utilizing PVGIS, a tool that delivers information about solar radiation and photovoltaic system performance [58], we optimize the slope and azimuth for Kyiv and Odesa (Table 56). The presence of a large roof area (~4760m²) indicates the huge potential to tap into the insolation and this translates to a calculated panel power of 351 kWp. Factoring in the area required for operation and maintenance and other equipment beside the panels, the generated electricity was found to be about 435MWh/a and 494MWh/for Kyiv and Odesa respectively. But, despite having optimized the positioning of the PV panels, the schools being on holiday during the months with very high PV production (July and August) acts as a deterrent to fulfil clause 6 by using only solar energy.

Table 56. PV parameters for the apartment building, Kyiv, and Odesa.

	Kyiv	Odesa
Panel slope, °	37	36
Panel azimuth, °	-2	1
System loss, %	14	14
Required area, m ² /kWp*	12	12
Available roof area, m ²	4760	4760
Panel power, kWp	351	351
Generated annual electricity, MWh	435	494

*Area practically required for south facing panels, considering walking paths and other equipment on the roof.

7.6.1 Kyiv region

The monthly in-plane irradiation for a fixed angle PV system for Kyiv is displayed in Figure 78. It should be understood that the monthly irradiation profile does not reflect how it behaves on an hourly level. With the operating hours of school only 10 hours a day (7-17 hours), without the presence of a storage device or the capacity to sell the excess PV back to the grid, only looking at the monthly irradiation data would not be fruitful.

Figure 78: Monthly in-plane irradiation for fixed angle in Kyiv

The PV-load matching was done for four different cases – the default case (Case I), improvements that led to least energy expended (Case II), improvements that led to least energy expended without the implementation of a ventilation heat recovery unit (Case III) and improvements that cost the least (Case IV). The plots for the monthly load-matching and the daily load-matching for the first week of January and the first week of June is depicted in the [Annex](#).

As stated earlier, the months of July and August have the least loads owing to holidays. It could also be seen that for cases I and III, the absence of a ventilation heat recovery unit is reflected in lesser electric loads. The consumption, generation and the matching factor are tabulated in Table 57. It should be noted that a maximum of 41% of its electrical consumption is matched solely by PV energy. A further addition of a battery system or exporting the PV back to the grid would result in improved matching and increased profits.

Table 57. PV matching for default, least energy and least cost scenarios, Kyiv.

Case	Gross electricity consumption [kWh/m ²]	PV generation [kWh/m ²]	Own use PV [kWh/m ²]	Own electricity fraction	Own electricity matching	Net cost without PV [k€]	Net cost with PV [k€]
Default	36.6	32.5	14.9	41 %	46 %	3411	3375
Least energy	73.2	32.5	22.0	30 %	68 %	2888	2654
Least energy without VHR	37.0	32.5	15.0	41 %	46 %	3461	3423
Least cost	71.2	32.5	21.9	31 %	67 %	2766	2534

*Own use PV / Gross electricity consumption

**Own use PV / PV generation

7.6.2 Odesa region

The monthly energy output from an optimized fix-angle PV system for Odesa is displayed in Figure 79. It is observed that Odesa, located in southern Ukraine, has a higher potential for PV as compared to Kyiv. At the same time, the warm climate necessitates a relatively increased cooling load.

Figure 79: Monthly in-plane irradiation for fixed angle in Odesa

The PV-load matching was done for four different cases – the default case (Case I), improvements that led to least energy expended (Case II), improvements that led to least energy expended without the implementation of a ventilation heat recovery unit (Case III) and improvements that cost the least (Case IV). The plots for the monthly load-matching and the daily load-matching for the first week of January and the first week of June are plotted in the [Annex](#).

As stated earlier, the months of July and August have the least loads owing to holidays. It could also be seen that for cases I and III, the absence of a ventilation heat recovery unit is reflected in lesser electric loads. The consumption, generation and the matching factor are tabulated in Table 58. It should be noted that a maximum of 48% of its electrical consumption is matched solely by PV energy. A further addition of a battery system or exporting the PV back to the grid would result in improved matching and increased profits.

Table 58. PV matching for default, least energy and least cost scenarios, Odesa.

Case	Gross electricity consumption [kWh/m ²]	PV generation [kWh/m ²]	Own use PV [kWh/m ²]	Own electricity fraction	Own electricity matching	Net cost without PV [k€]	Net cost with PV [k€]
Default	40.0	37.0	18.8	47 %	51 %	3831	3476

Least energy	75.7	37.0	25.8	34 %	70 %	3748	3119
Least energy without VHR	40.5	37.0	18.9	47 %	51 %	3906	3546
Least lifecycle cost	74.0	37.0	25.5	34 %	69 %	3551	2934

*Own use PV / Gross electricity consumption

**Own use PV / PV generation

8. NZEB recommendations based on the simulation study

This section includes discussion and recommendations based on the study results shown in earlier chapters. These results serve as an underlying support material for the development of technical recommendations for NZEB in Ukraine in the near future.

8.1 Apartment building

Energy efficient buildings are important to reduce the energy consumption, emissions and improve the indoor environment as needed in NZEB. For the apartment building, technical study in chapter 6.2 showed that on technically feasible level, ventilation heat recovery (VHR) has by far the highest potential for reducing heating energy use (heating consumption reduced 40-34 kWh/m² in apartment). Therefore, it is recommended to first concentrate on implementing VHR solutions. VHR was simulated as a centralized system, which requires ducting for supply and exhaust to each apartment. VHR can also be implemented by apartment-specific devices, which avoids this requirement, and similarly high level of energy consumption reduction can still be expected. However, integrating VHR to a centralized supply and exhaust system has the additional benefit of enabling better control of the indoor environment by centralized supply air heating and cooling. As recommended in order to include the VHR and ducting system in the buildings, the building design must incorporate and provide provision that will allow installation of air handling units and ducts. Additional space is needed to install unit in the buildings and fire safety hazard is also needed to be considered. Fire safety protocols must be included in the construction.

External wall U-value and window U-value improvements can also be implemented for considerable energy savings, while roof and floor improvements were shown to have minimal effect to the energy consumption of the apartment building.

The economical study for the apartment building in chapter 6.4 showed that from the chosen individual improvements, only VHR was found to be profitable in terms of total life cycle cost. Also, from the studied VHR options (low-end and high-end), the high-end device with 80 % efficiency is considerably more profitable and remains profitable even with 50 % increase in investment cost. Therefore, economically the main recommendation is to invest in a high-efficiency VHR improvement. Window improvements and external wall improvements are seen to become profitable if energy price increase of around 50 % were to take place. Therefore, the developments of improvement investment price and energy price determines their profitability in the future.

In the economic study, the default scenario and 3 specific improvement combination scenarios were selected for a closer look. Table 59 includes a summary of the impact of the scenarios on total purchased energy (including heating energy and all electricity use in the building) and life cycle cost in Kyiv climate zone.

Table 59: Selected scenarios of apartment building improvements, Kyiv.

Case	U-value [W/m ² K]				VHR efficiency [%]	Purchased energy consumption change	Life cycle cost change	Total primary energy consumption [kWh/m ² a]
	Window	External wall	Floor	Roof				
Default	1.11	0.25	0.2	0.17	0	-	-	199
Least energy without VHR	0.6	0.18	0.12	0.1	0	-7 %	+9 %	189
Least energy	0.6	0.18	0.12	0.1	80	-25 %	+5 %	173

Least cost	1.11	0.25	0.2	0.17	80	-21 %	-9 %	178
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It's seen the maximum achieved purchased energy change is 25 %, in which case LCC is increased by 5 %. This scenario includes all the improvements. However, if only VHR is implemented (least cost scenario), 21 % purchased energy is saved, and LCC is reduced by 9 %. Therefore, economically there is no incentive to implement improvements other than VHR.

Table 60 includes a summary of the impact of the scenarios on total purchased energy and life cycle cost in Odesa climate zone.

Table 60: Selected scenarios of apartment building improvements, Odesa

Case	U-value [W/m ² K]				VHR efficiency [%]	Purchased energy consumption change	Life cycle cost change	Total primary energy consumption [kWh/m ² /a]
	Window	External wall	Floor	Roof				
Default (Odesa)	1.43	0.29	0.25	0.18	0	-	-	196
Least energy without VHR	0.6	0.18	0.12	0.1	0	-10 %	+15 %	181
Least energy	0.6	0.18	0.12	0.1	80	-25 %	+15 %	170
Least cost	1.43	0.29	0.25	0.18	80	-20 %	-7 %	177

In the case of Odesa, the maximum achieved purchased energy change in the least energy case is 25 %, as it was in Kyiv. In this case LCC is increased by 15 %, which is higher than in Kyiv, since Odesa's investment starting level is lower. This scenario includes all the improvements. However, if only VHR is implemented, 20 % purchased energy is saved, and LCC is reduced by 7 %. Therefore, economically there is no incentive to implement improvements other than VHR.

It should be noted that the heating energy savings of U-value improvements are not reflected to same extent when it is coupled with the implementation of a VHR unit. The VHR unit results in a 'reduced heating season' and an 'extended cooling season' and the increased cooling is detrimental to the energy savings brought about by the structural improvements. As a result, mere improvements of all the components to the highest level need not necessarily translate into the best performance of the building.

With the used electricity tariff of 6 c/kWh for apartment buildings, PV investments are unprofitable both in Kyiv and Odesa. However, PV integration is beneficial to further reduce the energy consumption as required in NZEB (RE integration). Own electricity fraction with PV generation varied between 20% - 25%, and own electricity matching varied between 82% - 95%, with the higher value in Odesa. This shows that building roof area is limited, therefore most of the electricity was used to meet the onsite consumption. It is recommended to support the integration of PV by allowing onsite and nearby area to install PV (such as parking lots etc.).

8.2 School building

For the school building technical potential analysis showed that potential heating energy savings from ventilation heat recovery was found to enable at the most 90 % heating energy reduction, whereas the next most potential improvement, window U-value improvement, only enables around 4 % reduction. The potential of VHR is higher than for the apartment building due to higher ventilation flow rates (0.55 l/s/m² versus 1.84 l/s/m²) of the school building. Hence, as opposed to the current system of natural ventilation, from an energy saving point of view, the implementation

beyond the obvious

of a high efficiency VHR (80%) is recommended for school buildings. Window U-value improvements and roof improvements also seem to result in minimal energy savings, while also being profitable as compared to the base case scenario.

The economic study for the school building in chapter 7.4 showed that from individual improvements, window improvement level 1, roof improvement level 1 and both VHR improvements are profitable in terms of total life cycle cost. Also, from the studied VHR options (low-end and high-end), the high-end device with 80 % efficiency is considerably more profitable. Further, the default scenario and 3 specific improvement combination scenarios were also selected for a closer look. *Table 61* includes a summary of the impact of the scenarios on total purchased energy (including heating energy and all electricity use in the building) and life cycle cost in Kyiv climate zone.

Table 61: Selected scenarios of school building improvements, Kyiv.

Case	U-value [W/m ² K]				VHR efficiency [%]	Purchased energy consumption change	Life cycle cost change	Total primary energy consumption [kWh/m ² /a, kWh/m ³ /a]
	Window	External wall	Floor	Roof				
Default (Kyiv)	1.11	0.25	0.2	0.143	0	-	-	283, 61
Least energy without VHR	0.6	0.18	0.12	0.1	0	-4 %	+1 %	273, 59
Least energy	0.6	0.18	0.2	0.1	80	-45 %	-15 %	215, 46
Least cost	1.11	0.25	0.2	0.143	80	-44 %	-19 %	217, 47

It is seen the maximum achieved purchased energy change is 45 % (in the least energy scenario), in which case the life cycle cost is decreased by 15 %. This scenario includes all the improvements. However, if only VHR is implemented, 44 % purchased energy is saved, and LCC is reduced by 19 %.

Table 62 includes a summary of the impact of the scenarios on total purchased energy and life cycle cost in Odesa climate zone.

Table 62: Selected scenarios of school building improvements, Odesa

Case	U-value [W/m ² K]				VHR efficiency [%]	Purchased energy consumption change	Life cycle cost change	Total primary energy consumption [kWh/m ² /a, kWh/m ³ /a]
	Window	External wall	Floor	Roof				
Default (Odesa)	1.43	0.29	0.25	0.17	0	-	-	268, 58
Least energy without VHR	0.6	0.18	0.12	0.1	0	-6 %	+2 %	256, 55
Least energy	0.6	0.18	0.25	0.1	80	-43 %	-2 %	214, 46
Least cost	1.43	0.29	0.25	0.17	80	-41 %	-7 %	216, 46

In the case of Odesa, the maximum achieved purchased energy change in the least energy case is 43%, close to what was in Kyiv. In this case, the life cycle cost is decreased by only 2 %. This scenario includes all the improvements except the floor improvement. However, if only VHR is

implemented, there is a 41% reduction of purchased energy while cutting down the life cycle cost by 7%. Therefore, for maximal profitability only VHR should be implemented.

It should be noted that the heating energy savings of U-value improvements are not reflected to same extent when it is coupled with the implementation of a VHR unit. The VHR unit results in a 'reduced heating season' and an 'extended cooling season' and the increased cooling is detrimental to the energy savings brought about by the structural improvements. As a result, mere improvements of all the components to the highest level need not necessarily translate into the best performance of the building.

With high electricity tariffs of 15 c/kWh and 21 c/kWh for schools in Kyiv and Odesa respectively, PV integration is beneficial to cut down the total electricity prices and to further reduce the energy consumption as required in NZEB. Owing to a higher roof area as opposed to the apartment building, the school building's own electricity share varied between 30%- 47%, and own electricity matching varied between 46 - 70%. Lower electricity matching for school is partly due to the holiday season of two months during which the production is very high, but the electricity consumption is relatively low. Despite the lower own electricity matching compared to the apartment building, all studied PV scenarios for the school building were deemed profitable, due to the high electricity tariff. The adaptation of rooftop PV in school buildings could be facilitated even further, if feeding surplus PV electricity to the network, with a proper feed-in-tariff, were to be introduced.

In order to promote energy efficiency in the building sector that will support in reducing the emissions, energy consumption, energy import and improve the energy security, user comfort and indoor environment. It is recommended to provide support to the building sector in terms of regulations, policy and incentives. This would make energy efficient solutions for buildings (i.e. NZEB) and renewable energy integration economical and financial attractive. This will guide the local stakeholders, investors, companies, and end users to invest in energy efficient solutions. Support in terms of policy (regulations), reduce taxes, tax relief, incentive and interest rates reduction will provide support in making NZEB solutions economical and reduce the life cycle costs. With the expected increase in the energy cost in coming days, it is recommended to invest in energy efficient ventilation heat recovery unit (80%), efficient windows and walls in apartment building. This will reduce the LCC compared to present scenario, both for Kyiv and Odesa. It is recommended to invest in energy efficient ventilation heat recovery unit (80%), efficient windows, walls, floor, roof in school. This will already reduce the LCC compared to present scenario and will be beneficial with future energy cost, both for Kyiv and Odesa.

With the expected increase in the investment cost energy efficient solutions may be expensive in the apartment building case, however LCC will reduce eventually when the energy cost increases, both for Kyiv and Odesa. The energy efficient solutions are less expensive for school building, for Kyiv. The energy efficient solutions are slightly expensive for school building, for Odesa. Therefore, it is recommended to start implementing energy efficient solutions for schools already now.

Cooling system can also be integrated with the recommended ventilation systems in the building if ventilation units are used that can provide cool air. This can improve the overall indoor environment. In this project, district heating was studied and recommended for the buildings. District cooling is also another option that can be integrated with the buildings (similar to district heating). The district heating and cooling network can be coupled via heat pumps systems that can provide heating during winters and cooling during summers to the buildings. This can also help in recovering waste heat and improve the overall performance of NZEB building (by reducing the overall energy consumption). The overall cooling consumption of the buildings can be reduced through passive methods that is by controlling the opening of the windows during summers (using free cooling) and by using fixed and moveable shadings. PV as recommended in the report can be integrated to run cooling systems.

With the new financial channels, green financing, green deal and investors growing interest in the energy efficient solutions (for buildings) it is recommended to channelize the funding in reducing the investment cost for ventilation systems, windows, walls material. Support end users through policy by providing additional financial benefits for implementing energy efficient solutions. Provide easy loans conditions and reduced interests. In addition to the cost benefits, energy efficiency and renewable energy integration, it is recommended to provide capacity building and competence development in the construction and building sector that can provide fast transition towards NZEB and positive energy buildings. The investment channel can be used to further upgrade the skills of skilled manpower who can design, plan, install, operate, and maintain these solutions. Similar findings were found during the stakeholders workshop, therefore these recommendations are needed to further develop NZEB related projects and its implementation in Ukraine.

It is further recommended to provide policy support by improving the regulations that would make it necessary to integrate renewables with the apartment and school buildings. Integration of PV can be further supported by providing policy support to apartment and schools that gives tax benefits, better selling price, net metering availability and easy contracts.

Façade and windows could also be included in the regulations as a place where PV can be integrated. In addition, PV, heat pumps and energy storage should be integrated to further reduce the energy consumption. Regulations should support all new apartment and school buildings to include PV and other renewables from the planning stages. Regulations should also support new business models that will integrate PV and renewables with the building. This will support the local market, regulators, businesses, and end users to include PV and other renewables in the new construction from the beginning.

Moreover, the integration of PV can be further supported by providing tax benefits for investments, better market price, new business models and easy contracts. In order to move from NZEB towards positive energy buildings and to create energy communities it is recommended to provide regulatory support that will promote sharing of electricity to the grid, net metering options, market price to the end users, keeping end user at the core of decision making. The renewable energy integration can be support further by providing less expensive energy storage (batteries, heat storage etc.).

9. Beyond NZEB in Ukraine towards positive energy buildings

As an EU candidate, in the future, Ukraine is expected to comply with the directives governing EU countries.

9.1 Requirements of Nearly zero energy buildings

The Energy Performance of Buildings directive [60](EPBD), together with the Energy Efficiency Directive [61](EED) and the Renewable Energy Directive (RED) [62] formulate a package of measures for significant and long-term improvements in the energy performance of Europe's building stock. The EPBD states that all new buildings are Nearly zero-energy buildings (NZEBs) that "have a very high energy performance with the nearly zero or very low amount of energy required covered to a very significant extent by energy from renewable sources, including energy from renewable sources produced on-site or nearby".

The first part of this definition establishes energy performance as the defining element that makes a building an 'NZEB'. This energy performance must be very high. According to the Annex I of the Directive the energy performance can be determined based on the calculated or actual annual energy that is consumed to meet the needs associated with its typical use (residential or non-

residential) and shall reflect the heating energy needs and cooling energy needs (energy needed to avoid overheating) to maintain the envisaged temperature conditions of the building, and domestic hot water needs. The second part of the definition provides guiding principles to achieve this very high energy performance by covering the resulting low amount of energy to a very significant extent by energy from renewable sources.

The present EPBD does not provide minimum or maximum harmonized requirements for NZEBs. The Directive requires Member States to define the detailed application in practice of “a very high energy performance” and the recommendation of “a very significant extent by energy from renewable sources, in line with their local characteristics and national contexts. Table 63 just reports the benchmarks for the energy performance of NZEBs in different climatic zones per building type (single family houses and offices).

The energy performance of a building shall be expressed in a transparent manner and shall include an energy performance indicator and a numeric indicator of primary energy use, based on primary energy factors per energy carrier, which may be based on national or regional annual weighted averages or a specific value for on-site production.

Table 63. NZEB level of energy performance (kWh/m²/y) per building type and climatic zone [63].

Type of building	NZEB RECOMMENDATION BENCHMARK	
	Net primary energy use (on-site RES excluded) kWh/(m ² y)	Primary energy use kWh/(m ² y)
MEDITERRANEAN (CY, HR, IT, GR, MT, PT ES)		
Single family houses	0-15	50-65
Offices	20-30	80-90
OCEANIC (BE, DK, IE, DE, FR, LU, NL, UK)		
Single family houses	15-30	50-65
Offices	40-55	85-100
CONTINENTAL (AT, BG, CZ, HU, PL, RO, SL, SK)		
Single family houses	20-40	50-70
Offices	40-55	85-100
NORDIC (EE, FI, LV, LT, SE)		
Single family houses	40-65	65-90
Offices	55-70	85-100

9.2 Requirements of zero-emission buildings

The recast of EPBD [64] has the former definition of NZEBs. They are “buildings with a very high energy performance, The nearly zero or very low amount of energy required is covered to a very significant extent by energy from renewable sources, including energy from renewable sources produced on-site or nearby”.

As a whole new goal, EPBD recast brings to the table the zero-emission building, what means “a building with a very high energy performance, where nearly zero or very low amount of energy required is covered to a very significant extent by energy from renewable sources, including energy from renewable sources produced on-site or nearby”. Also, a zero-emission building must not cause any on-site carbon emissions from fossil fuels. This requirement for new buildings will come into force gradually over the years 2028-2030.

The total annual primary energy use of a new or renovated zero -emission building is covered, where technically and economically feasible by a) energy from renewable sources generated onsite or nearby; (b) energy from renewable sources provided from a renewable energy community; or (c) energy from an efficient district heating and cooling system. Energy from renewable sources means energy from renewable non-fossil sources, namely wind, solar (solar **beyond the obvious**

thermal and solar photovoltaic) and geothermal energy, ambient energy, tide, wave and other ocean energy, hydropower, biomass, landfill gas, sewage treatment plant gas, and biogas.

What is relevant is the definition of zero-emission building is the factor used to calculate the primary energy. The calculation of primary energy will be based on primary energy factors (distinguishing non-renewable, renewable, and total) per energy carrier. The primary energy factors can be based on national, regional, or local information. Primary energy factors can be set on an annual, seasonal, monthly, daily, or even hourly basis or on more specific information made available for individual district systems.

Also, all new buildings must be designed to optimise their solar energy generation potential based on the solar irradiance of the site, enabling the later cost-effective installation of solar technologies. This requirement will come into force gradually over the years 2027-2030.

9.3 Positive energy buildings

Based on scientific studies [65], the unofficial definition of the Positive energy building (PEB) is “an energy-efficient building that produces more energy than it uses via renewable sources, with high self-consumption rate and high energy flexibility, over a time span of one year. A high-quality indoor environment is an essential element in the PEB, maintaining the building occupants’ comfort and well-being. The PEB can also integrate future technologies like electric vehicles with the motivation to maximize the onsite consumption and share the surplus renewable energy.”

In PEBs, energy flexibility is an important aspect, facilitating the reduction of the mismatch between the energy consumption and energy generation from renewables. Furthermore, the appropriate technical solutions for the PEB depend highly on the location and climate. For example, a high seasonal variance of energy needs and supply (Nordic Europe), makes it more demanding to build PEB than whereas lots of solar energy throughout the year is available (Southern Europe).

An example of a PEB [66] built in the Continental climate zone. The declared objective of this high-rise building is to achieve a positive energy building (PEB) standard, in other words annual accumulated local generation exceeding total consumption. To reach this goal, several energy efficiency measures are integrated, including a highly insulated, prefabricated, active curtain façade, new heat pumps, façade integrated PV, thermal- and electrical storages. The most prominent feature of the new energy design is the large thermally activated concrete mass, as the existing structure is conditioned via active layers within the new façade. The thermal storage created by this measure provides the energy flexibility needed to reach high coherence between electricity generation and consumption. The users are involved with an energy community control system and a smart energy billing concept. As a summary, the prerequisite for meeting the PEB standard is own energy production, smart structural and technical systems, energy storage, as well as active participation of residents.

10. Conclusions and summary

This report and project address the challenges and opportunities in the building sector in Ukraine toward the carbon neutral energy efficient buildings. The project's aim and scope are to provide and assist the Ministry of Development of Communities and Territories of Ukraine in developing the technical recommendation for nearly zero energy building (NZEB) in Ukraine, like the EU's Energy performance building directives (EPBD). This is becoming more important when the reconstruction of buildings and re-habitation of the cities begin. Energy efficiency will also help in reducing the emissions, energy import, energy security therefore political support is needed

Two building types were studied residential apartment building (10900 m² heated floor area) and school building (13365 m² heated floor area) in Kyiv and Odesa region. The outcome of the simulation work of the representative buildings are presented below:

Apartment building

Technical potential of improvements

For heating energy savings, ventilation heat recovery has by far the best technical potential. Second best is window U-value improvement, and third external wall U-value improvement. Floor and roof U-value improvements were found to have negligible impact. Most U-value improvements caused an increase in cooling load, since higher insulation means the building will retain its heat more effectively in the summer. Ventilation heat recovery increased cooling consumption in Kyiv region, due to better insulation of the building and due to higher heat recovery efficiency. This can be reduced by bypassing the heat recovery unit during summers, using shading of the windows and by opening the windows in summers. In Odessa region free cooling is scarcely available in the summer, therefore the increase of cooling is less.

Improvement combinations and economical potential

Net present value was calculated for combinations of chosen discrete improvements. Ventilation heat recovery was found to be the only individual profitable improvement. Other improvements can also be combined with the ventilation heat recovery to be profitable, but the ventilation heat recovery reduces the effectiveness for other improvements, since it effectively shortens the heating season (and lengthens the cooling season, unless bypass is used during summer). The result was similar for both Kyiv and Odesa.

A sensitivity analysis was done for the economical profitability of selected cases. If energy prices increase, the LCC of cases with higher energy consumption increases more. If energy prices were to increase 50%, the case with all the improvements (LE) would become profitable, if they were to increase 100%, also the case with only structural improvements would become profitable with discount rate of 25 % instead of 8 %, none of the improvements were profitable. The situation applies for both Kyiv and Odesa.

Photovoltaic

Techno-economic potential of rooftop PV was studied separately for four scenarios. For the apartment building the rooftop area is relatively small compared to building total area. As a result, only 20 – 25 % of the building's electricity consumption could be covered with a rooftop PV installation. On the other hand, most of PV production is consumed on-site, with OEM of 83 % - 95 % between the studied cases. The studied PV cases with ventilation HR exhibits higher OEM, since the introduction of mechanical ventilation increases the building's electricity consumption. PV was unprofitable in all the studied scenarios, although by smaller margin in cases with mechanical ventilation and higher OEM.

School building

Technical potential of improvements

The main studied components were the ventilation heat recovery unit and the U-values of the external wall, roof, floor and windows.

1. Among the studied components, the implementation of a ventilation heat recovery unit and improving its efficiency has by far the largest heating energy saving potential. Presently, buildings in Ukraine have no means of recovering ventilation air energy, whereas for U-values, relatively stringent requirements are already in place.
2. The window improvements are found to bring about a maximum of 4% reduction in heating demand, whereas the external wall improvements are found to have reduced the heating demand by a maximum of 3% for the studied U-values
3. Improving the U-values of the roof and the floor was found to have minimal effect on the energy demand of the building

Improvement combinations and economical potential

The implementation of a ventilation heat recovery unit reduces the overall life cycle cost in Kyiv. Amongst the two improvement levels of the heat recovery unit, 40% efficiency and 80% efficiency, the latter was found to result in greatest cost savings. Individual roof and window improvements to level one also resulted in a lesser cost as compared to the default baseline scenario. However, combined with VHR this was no longer the case, as similarly to the apartment building, ventilation heat recovery reduces the effectiveness for other improvements, since it effectively shortens the heating season (and lengthens the cooling season, unless bypass is used during summer).

For Odesa, owing to the quite high (0.21€/kWh) electricity tariff, only a ventilation heat recovery unit with 80% efficiency results in a reduced cost as compared to default case. Individual roof and window improvements to level one also resulted in less cost as compared to the default baseline scenario.

Photovoltaic

The school building has higher rooftop area per heated area, compared to the apartment building. As a result, higher own energy fraction is achieved, 30 – 41 % in Kyiv and 34 – 47 % in Odesa. The studied PV case with ventilation HR was found profitable, due to the high electricity tariff (15-21 c/kWh for school compared to 6 c/kWh for apartment building) and high flow rates of mechanical ventilation causing high electricity expenses otherwise.

In addition, the presence of a battery or a storage solution would result in an increasing matching factor and thereby, reduces the need of imported electricity. In addition, the government should investigate the possibility of consumers selling the excess PV electricity back to the grid, as this would bring economic benefits for the households while also being a solution to reduce import from other countries.

In this project, district heating was studied and recommended for the buildings. District cooling is also another option that can be integrated with the buildings (similar to district heating). The district heating and cooling network can be coupled via heat pumps systems that can provide heating during winters and cooling during summers to the buildings. This can also help in recovering waste heat and improve the overall performance of NZEB building (by reducing the overall energy consumption). The overall cooling consumption of the buildings can be reduced through passive methods that is by controlling the opening of the windows during summers (using free cooling) and by using fixed and moveable shadings. PV as recommended in the report can be integrated to run cooling systems.

New financial channels, green financing and investors growing interest in the energy efficient solutions (for buildings) it is recommended to channelize the funding in reducing the investment cost for ventilation systems, windows, walls material. Support end users through policy by providing additional financial benefits for implementing energy efficient solutions. Provide easy loans conditions and reduced interests. In addition to the cost benefits, energy efficiency and renewable energy integration, it is recommended to provide capacity building and competence development in the construction and building sector that can provide fast transition towards NZEB and positive energy buildings. Similar findings were found during the stakeholders workshop, therefore these recommendations are needed to further develop NZEB related projects and its implementation in Ukraine.

Future Projects

Following projects and scope in Ukraine can be developed as continuation of this work. These scopes are defined based on the discussions and feedback from the stakeholders in Ukraine.

- NZEB Building regulations for other new buildings type (single family house, daycares, hospital, commercial, offices etc.) in different climate in Ukraine
- Building renovation and NZEB regulations for old and renovated buildings (reconstruction)
- Improvements and regulations improvements for appliances, lights etc. Improved system for cooling, windows controls, ventilation
- Low carbon buildings, wooden structure buildings for fast construction and lower costs (reconstruction)
- Distributed/local renewable sources in Ukraine – the most relevant/realistic (reconstruction)
- Renewable energy sources integration with the building such as: heat pumps, biomass, biofuels, solar thermal, wind
- Integration of energy storage, electrical and heat storages
- Energy performance certificate regulations, directives and policy upgrade
- Building permits upgrade
- Barriers to energy efficiency and NZEB solutions
- Positive and zero emissions buildings, energy communities (reconstruction)
- Capacity building and competence development in construction and building sector towards NZEB and positive energy buildings (reconstruction)
- Demo cases of NZEBs

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12. Abbreviations

°C	Centigrade
CAD	Computer aided design
CMC	Coordination and Management Consultant for the FUTF
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
COP	Conference of the Parties
DHW	Domestic hot water
EE	Energy efficiency
EPBD	Energy performance of Buildings Directive
EU	European Union
FUTF	Finland Ukraine Trust Fund
HVAC	Heating, ventilation, and air conditioning
HX	Heat exchanger
IEA	International energy agency
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IDA ICE	Indoor Climate and Energy
K	Kelvin
KSE	Kyiv School of Economics
LCC	Life cycle cost
m	Meter
NDC	Nationally determined contributions
NMF	Neutral Model Format
NZEB	Nearly zero energy building
OEF	Own energy factor
OEM	Own energy matching
PEX	Cross-Linked Polyethylene
PV	Photovoltaic
R-value	Thermal resistance
RED	Renewable energy directive

RES	Renewable energy source
U-value	Thermal transmittance
UN	United Nation
VHR	Ventilation Heat Recovery
W	Watt
WP	Work package

Appendices

Appendix 1 - 1st Workshop with the stakeholders

Appendix 2 - 2nd Workshop with the stakeholders

Appendix 3 - 3rd Workshop with the stakeholders

Appendix 4 - Apartment model input data report

 SIMULATION TECHNOLOGY GROUP		<h2>Input data Report</h2>	
Project		Building	
Customer		Model floor area	12060.1 m ²
Created by	Andrei Wallin	Model volume	35357.9 m ³
Location	Kyiv_333450 (ASHRAE 2013)	Model ground area	1144.4 m ²
Climate file	UKR_KYIV_333450(IW2)	Model envelope area	8213.9 m ²
Case	Final	Window/Envelope	22.7 %
Simulated	3.11.2022 15.54.18	Average U-value	0.4345 W/(m ² K)
		Envelope area per Volume	0.2323 m ² /m ³

Fixed infiltration airflow rate			1276.850 l/s	
Building envelope	Area [m ²]	U [W/(m ² K)]	U*A [W/K]	% of total
Walls above ground	3783.17	0.25	950.30	26.63
External wall (new)	3783.17	0.25	950.30	26.63
Walls below ground	280.04	0.13	36.27	1.02
External wall (new)	280.04	0.13	36.27	1.02
Roof	1134.64	0.36	402.80	11.29
Technical floor roof	1134.64	0.35	402.80	11.29
Floor towards ground	1144.42	0.09	100.54	2.82
Floor (new)	1144.42	0.09	100.54	2.82
Floor towards amb. air	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Windows	1865.21	1.11	2070.38	58.01
Window (minimum regulation)	1865.21	1.11	2070.38	58.01
Doors	6.40	1.34	8.57	0.24
Door (minimum regulation)	6.40	1.34	8.57	0.24
Thermal bridges			0.00	0.00
Total	8213.88	0.43	3568.87	100.00

Thermal bridges	Area or Length	Avg. Heat conductivity	Total [W/K]
External wall / internal slab	3580.54 m	0.000 W/(m K)	0.000
External wall / internal wall	797.99 m	0.000 W/(m K)	0.000
External wall / external wall	624.30 m	0.000 W/(m K)	0.000
External windows perimeter	5374.88 m	0.000 W/(m K)	0.000
External doors perimeter	14.40 m	0.000 W/(m K)	0.000
Roof / external walls	197.47 m	0.000 W/(m K)	0.000
External slab / external walls	182.76 m	0.000 W/(m K)	0.000
Balcony floor / external walls	0.00 m	0.000 W/(K m)	0.000
External slab / Internal walls	0.00 m	0.000 W/(K m)	0.000
Roof / Internal walls	438.71 m	0.000 W/(m K)	0.000
External walls, inner corner	517.99 m	0.000 W/(m K)	0.000
Roof / external walls, inner corner	3.94 m	0.000 W/(m K)	0.000
External slab / external walls, inner corner	28.94 m	0.000 W/(m K)	0.000
Total envelope (incl. roof and ground)	8146.25 m ²	0.000 W/(m ² K)	0.000
Extra losses	-	-	0.000
Sum	-	-	0.000

Windows	Area [m ²]	U Glass [W/(m ² K)]	U Frame [W/(m ² K)]	U Total [W/(m ² K)]	U*A [W/K]	Shading factor g
N	698.95	1.11	1.11	1.11	775.83	0.68
NE	162.00	1.11	1.11	1.11	179.82	0.68
SE	76.50	1.11	1.11	1.11	84.91	0.68
S	691.52	1.11	1.11	1.11	767.58	0.68
SW	76.50	1.11	1.11	1.11	84.91	0.68
NW	159.75	1.11	1.11	1.11	177.32	0.68
Total	1865.21	1.11	1.11	1.11	2070.38	0.68

Air handling unit	Pressure head supply/exhaust [Pa/Pa]	Fan efficiency supply/exhaust [-/-]	System SFP [kW/(m ³ /s)]	Heat exchanger temp. ratio/min exhaust temp. [-/°C]
AHU	600.00/400.00	0.60/0.60	1.00/0.67	0.00/1.00
Technical floor AHU	600.00/400.00	0.60/0.60	1.00/0.67	0.00/1.00

Appendix 5 - School building model input data report

		<h3>Input data Report</h3>	
Project		Building	
Customer		Model floor area	13364.8 m ²
Created by	Rakesh Ramesh	Model volume	62241.4 m ³
Location	Kyiv_333450 (ASHRAE 2013)	Model ground area	4784.2 m ²
Climate file	UKR_KYIV_333450(IW2)	Model envelope area	15575.3 m ²
Case	andreidiea2_defaultkyiv	Window/Envelope	12.0 %
Simulated	31.10.2022 11.36.26	Average U-value	0.2726 W/(m ² K)
		Envelope area per Volume	0.2502 m ² /m ³

Fixed infiltration airflow rate			1728.874 l/s	
Building envelope	Area [m ²]	U [W/(m ² K)]	U*A [W/K]	% of total
Walls above ground	4085.69	0.25	1021.00	24.05
external wall irpin1	4085.69	0.25	1021.00	24.05
Walls below ground	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Roof	4759.57	0.14	678.20	15.98
roof irpin1	4759.57	0.14	678.20	15.98
Floor towards ground	4784.21	0.08	369.80	8.71
final floor irpin external2	4784.21	0.08	369.80	8.71
Floor towards amb. air	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Windows	1873.44	1.11	2079.52	48.99
window irpin1	1873.44	1.11	2079.52	48.99
Doors	72.39	1.33	96.36	2.27
door irpin2	72.39	1.33	96.36	2.27
Thermal bridges			0.00	0.00
Total	15575.31	0.27	4244.88	100.00

Thermal bridges	Area or Length	Avg. Heat conductivity	Total [W/K]
External wall / internal slab	1577.39 m	0.000 W/(m K)	0.000
External wall / internal wall	990.40 m	0.000 W/(m K)	0.000
External wall / external wall	349.57 m	0.000 W/(m K)	0.000
External windows perimeter	2475.93 m	0.000 W/(m K)	0.000
External doors perimeter	115.34 m	0.000 W/(m K)	0.000
Roof / external walls	535.51 m	0.000 W/(m K)	0.000
External slab / external walls	438.18 m	0.000 W/(m K)	0.000
Balcony floor / external walls	0.00 m	0.000 W/(K m)	0.000
External slab / Internal walls	0.00 m	0.000 W/(K m)	0.000
Roof / Internal walls	1553.39 m	0.000 W/(m K)	0.000
External walls, inner corner	241.86 m	0.000 W/(m K)	0.000
Roof / external walls, inner corner	29.84 m	0.000 W/(m K)	0.000
External slab / external walls, inner corner	0.19 m	0.000 W/(m K)	0.000
Total envelope (incl. roof and ground)	15484.33 m ²	0.000 W/(m ² K)	0.000
Extra losses	-	-	0.000
Sum	-	-	0.000

Windows	Area [m ²]	U Glass [W/(m ² K)]	U Frame [W/(m ² K)]	U Total [W/(m ² K)]	U*A [W/K]	Shading factor g
N	574.52	1.11	1.11	1.11	637.72	0.68
E	358.37	1.11	1.11	1.11	397.80	0.68
S	677.16	1.11	1.11	1.11	751.65	0.68
W	263.38	1.11	1.11	1.11	292.36	0.68
Total	1873.44	1.11	1.11	1.11	2079.52	0.68

Air handling unit	Pressure head supply/exhaust [Pa/Pa]	Fan efficiency supply/exhaust [-/-]	System SFP [kW/(m ³ /s)]	Heat exchanger temp. ratio/min exhaust temp. [-/°C]
AHU	600.00/400.00	0.60/0.60	1.00/0.67	0.00/1.00

DHW use	kWh/m ² floor area and year	Total, [l/s]
	10.000	0.073

Appendix 6 – PV integration and load-matching

A 6.1 Apartment Building

Kyiv region

Figure 80: (top) Monthly load-matching plot for the apartment building in Kyiv, (middle) daily load-matching for the first week of January and (bottom) daily load-matching for the first week of June – Case I. The final electricity consumption and PV production is shown in the figure.

Figure 81: (top) Monthly load-matching plot for the apartment building in Kyiv, (middle) daily load-matching for the first week of January and (bottom) daily load-matching for the first week of June – Case II. The final electricity consumption and PV production is shown in the figure.

Figure 82: (top) Monthly load-matching plot for the apartment building in Kyiv, (middle) daily load-matching for the first week of January and (bottom) daily load-matching for the first week of June – Case III. The final electricity consumption and PV production is shown in the figure.

Figure 83: (top) Monthly load-matching plot for the apartment building in Kyiv, (middle) daily load-matching for the first week of January and (bottom) daily load-matching for the first week of June – Case IV. The final electricity consumption and PV production is shown in the figure.

Figure 84: (top) Monthly load-matching plot for the apartment building in Odesa, (middle) daily load-matching for the first week of January and (bottom) daily load-matching for the first week of June – Case I. The final electricity consumption and PV production is shown in the figure.

Figure 85: (top) Monthly load-matching plot for the apartment building in Odesa, (middle) daily load-matching for the first week of January and (bottom) daily load-matching for the first week of June – Case II. The final electricity consumption and PV production is shown in the figure.

Figure 86: Monthly load-matching plot for the apartment building in Odesa, (middle) daily load-matching for the first week of January and (bottom) daily load-matching for the first week of June – Case III. The final electricity consumption and PV production is shown in the figure.

Figure 87: Monthly load-matching plot for the apartment building in Odesa, (middle) daily load-matching for the first week of January and (bottom) daily load-matching for the first week of June – Case IV. The final electricity consumption and PV production is shown in the figure.

A 6.2 School Building

Kyiv region

Figure 88: (top) Monthly load-matching plot for the school in Kyiv, (middle) daily load-matching for the first week of January, and (bottom) daily load-matching for the first week of June – Case I. The final electricity consumption and PV production is shown in the figure.

Figure 89: (top) Monthly load-matching plot for the school in Kyiv (middle) daily load-matching for the first week of January and (bottom) daily load-matching for the first week of June – Case II. The final electricity consumption and PV production is shown in the figure.

Figure 90: (top) Monthly load-matching plot for the school in Kyiv (middle) daily load-matching for the first week of January and (bottom) daily load-matching for the first week of June – Case III. The final electricity consumption and PV production is shown in the figure.

Figure 91: (top) Monthly load-matching plot for the school in Kyiv (middle) daily load-matching for the first week of January and (bottom) daily load-matching for the first week of June – Case IV. The final electricity consumption and PV production is shown in the figure.

Odesa region

Figure 92: (top) Monthly load-matching plot for the school in Odesa, (middle) daily load-matching for the first week of January, and (bottom) daily load-matching for the first week of June – Case I. The final electricity consumption and PV production is shown in the figure.

Figure 93: (top) Monthly load-matching plot for the school in Odesa, (middle) daily load-matching for the first week of January and (bottom) daily load-matching for the first week of June – Case II. The final electricity consumption and PV production is shown in the figure.

Figure 94: (top) Monthly load-matching plot for the school in Odesa (middle) daily load-matching for the first week of January and (bottom) daily load-matching for the first week of June – Case III. The final electricity consumption and PV production is shown in the figure.

Figure 95: (top) Monthly load-matching plot for the school in Odesa, (middle) daily load-matching for the first week of January and (bottom) daily load-matching for the first week of June – Case IV. The final electricity consumption and PV production is shown in the figure.